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The Academic Chronicles of Mathematics Quizzers: A Narratology

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Abstract

The main objective of this qualitative study was to aim and understand the academic chronicles among mathematics quizzers. Using purposive sampling, 14 mathematics students from a public school's mathematics quiz team were selected as participants. All of them participated in an in-depth study. The results revealed the participants' experiences, including the challenges they faced as mathematics quizzers. Having the feeling of satisfaction and fun in mathematics; collaborative learning enhances mathematical understanding; and lack of self-confidence causing learning deficiency. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deemed the following coping strategies essential: embodying the practical importance of mathematics; mentor support and motivation; emulating positive mindset and perseverance; and practicing self-preparation strategies, they arrived at the following insights: reflections on the importance of active learning and persistence; perseverance and growth mindset in mathematics; integration of technology for enhanced engagement and learning; and overcoming math challenges through effort and engagement. The results of this study were anticipated to be meaningful and important to the participants, teachers, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *academic chronicles, mathematics quizzers, narratological approach, qualitative research, Philippines*

Introduction

The academic chronicles of mathematics quizzers significantly hinder students' competitive performance. A critical issue is the intense pressure quizzers face during competitions, which prioritizes speed and memorization over genuine comprehension of mathematical concepts. This narrow focus on rapid recall limits their ability to develop essential problem-solving and critical thinking skills, undermining long-term academic success. Furthermore, the inconsistent availability of resources, such as advanced coaching and specialized study materials, results in uneven preparation among quizzers, exacerbating disparities in competition readiness. This gap not only affects individual performance but also disrupts team dynamics, making it difficult for students to collaborate effectively in high-pressure environments. Addressing these serious concerns is crucial to creating an equitable and supportive framework for both academic and competitive success (Mozharov et al., 2019).

In global settings, academic chronicles of mathematics quizzers often find themselves challenges impacting their competitive experiences. A prominent issue is the high levels of anxiety that quizzers face during timed quizzes, which can hinder their ability to effectively utilize problem-solving strategies. This anxiety often stems from the pressure to perform well, especially when competing against peers. Additionally, disparities in access to supplemental resources—such as specialized math coaching or quality study materials—create unequal preparation opportunities, which can adversely affect their performance. Furthermore, uneven participation in group study sessions is a concern, as some quizzers may depend on others for answers, limiting their engagement in the learning process. These challenges not only affect individual performances but also disrupt team dynamics in competitions. Addressing these issues is essential for fostering a more supportive environment, ultimately enhancing the success of all mathematics quizzers in their academic pursuits (Rauf, M. 2020).

In the Philippines, mathematics quizzer performance has decreased dramatically, as indicated by the country's last-place placement among 58 countries in grade 4 mathematics and science in the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS). Mathematics quizzers at New Corella National High School face several issues that significantly affect both their well-being and performance. One of the most pressing concerns is the high level of stress and anxiety they experience during competitions, which can lead to mental fatigue, reduced motivation, and fear of failure. This anxiety often diminishes their self-confidence and discourages future participation in quiz events. Additionally, the competitive atmosphere tends to push quizzers toward rote memorization rather than fostering a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts. This focus on short-term success can hinder their long-term academic growth and limit their ability to apply mathematical knowledge in creative, real-world scenarios. Addressing these challenges is crucial for creating a more supportive and balanced environment for mathematics quizzers, promoting both their academic and emotional well-being (Jones et al 2024).

Additionally, this inquiry highlights the critical need to understand the experiences and problems encountered by mathematics quizzers, who are frequently disregarded despite their ability to flourish in STEM subjects. Highlighting their academic trajectories, this study can identify important characteristics that contribute to or hurdle their achievement, providing valuable information for educators and policymakers. Socially, this study emphasizes the necessity of developing young mathematicians, which is critical for fostering creativity and competitiveness in a quickly changing technological world. Furthermore, it can foster a greater acceptance of varied learning methods and promote equity in educational opportunities for all children.

Furthermore, this study seeks to fill a substantial research gap by providing a thorough narrative-based inquiry into math quizzers'

academic paths. While earlier studies have provided insightful information, a more comprehensive knowledge of the varied experiences of math quiz takers is still lacking. In 'Lived Experiences of the International Mathematics Competition Winners: A Phenomenographic Study,' for example, Labis (2022) delves deeply into the lives of competition winners. This study's scope is restricted to a certain subset of quizzers, which limits its application and breadth to the larger quizzing population, even if it provides in-depth insights into the phenomenological features of successful competitors.

Similar to this, Jose (2022) offers insightful localized data in 'Factors That Affect the Performance of Selected High School Students from the Third District of Albay in International Mathematics Competitions,' but it is not universally applicable. Although these studies are enlightening, they highlight a crucial vacuum in the research that needs to be filled: a comprehensive perspective that considers the diverse, worldwide experiences of all math exam takers rather than simply the exceptional or isolated cases. By filling this knowledge gap, our research hopes to create more specialized and efficient assistance plans that consider the particular requirements and difficulties faced by math quizzers around the globe, improving their academic performance as well as their personal growth. This approach not only captures the diverse experiences and challenges faced by these students but also provides a holistic understanding of the factors that influence their academic and personal development.

Upon completion of this research, the researcher plan to submit the research paper to the Department of Education (DepEd). This study intends to provide insights that can help improve the learning environments for these kids, thereby aiding their mathematical progress. The primary goal is to build a firm basis that will allow the DepEd to design strategies and policies that encourage more effective learning environments, assisting students in improving their mathematical abilities. Furthermore, the researchers intend to publish the study in the hopes that it would be a useful resource for other academics interested in furthering this research, maybe on a national or international scale. By disseminating these results, the study hopes to improve knowledge of the difficulties experienced by students in mathematical competitions and establish itself as a major point of reference and inspiration for additional investigation. This communication aims to increase understanding of these issues not only in the New Corella local context but also in a number of other educational settings.

Research Questions

The study aimed to provide insight into the world of mathematics quizzers in New Corella, Davao del Norte. This study intends to explore the varied problems that these students confront while preparing for competitive mathematics competitions by diving into their life experiences. Understanding the challenges students confront, whether due to academic pressure, time limits, or resource constraints, can give light on the complex terrain of competitive mathematics in public schools.

Furthermore, examining the coping methods used by these quizzers to manage these hurdles will not only show their resilience, but will also provide insights into prospective support systems and ideas for improvement within the educational environment. Finally, this study aims to provide practical insights to improve the learning experiences and competition readiness of regional mathematics quizzers. The study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of mathematics quizzers?
2. How do these mathematics quizzers cope with the challenges they have experienced?
3. What insights can be obtained from these mathematics quizzers that can be shared to other mathematics quizzers and to the academe in general?

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, a qualitative research method was incorporated a narratological approach. Focused specifically on examining the observer who was immersed in the reality of the world, collecting and analyzing non-numerical data for a comprehensive understanding of the thoughts, ideas, and experiences of the participants. Through this design, the researcher gathered in-depth insights that produced new ideas for the study, taken from the participants involved in the event (Bhandari, 2023).

In the context of the study, qualitative research design was used because it was the ideal method for this study, which was concerned with a less explored research topic. This gained deep understanding about the mathematics quizzers who had experienced deficiency in developing and using effective study skills. All data were gathered through one-on-one conversations called in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

The study employed a method known as narratology, which focused on the insights, coping mechanisms, and experiences of individuals involved with the phenomenon. Through this qualitative research design, participants' experiences were revealed by gathering in-depth information and perspectives via conversations and interviews. The data collected were meticulously examined, organized, and connected through similar terms and themes, providing a comprehensive understanding of the topic under investigation. In this study, narratology was used to explore the academic chronicles of participants within a local context in Davao del Norte. This approach proved to be highly suitable for the topic, as it effectively navigated the academic experiences of the participants through the lens of narratology.

Participants

The participants of the study were high school students who participated in mathematics quizzes served as the primary subjects of this study. In particular, there was a total of 14 people in the group, which was the appropriate range of participants in a narratological study (Parse, 1990).

The 14 participants in this study were chosen by the researcher using the purposive sampling technique. The purposeful selection of an informant was based on the informant's personal characteristics, known as judgment sampling or purposive sampling technique. It was a non-random technique that did not call for a predetermined number of informants or underlying ideas. Simply put, the researcher selected what information was necessary to have and then searched for individuals who could and were willing to supply it due to their knowledge or experience (Bernard, 2002; Lewis & Sheppard, 2006).

Procedure

According to Creswell (2013), the following are generally considered to be the phases of data collection: acquiring access to data sources; building rapport with participants; using purposive sampling; recording information; addressing field concerns; collecting data; and storing data. The lead investigator in this investigation followed a set procedure to gather the necessary data and information before starting this study. I made sure my manuscript was examined by the technical review panel and the research adviser who had been assigned to me before the study was carried out. They granted me the all-clear to perform my study after I passed the rigorous assessment of it, which included the validation of the interview guide.

Second, the approach of purposive sampling was used to start the data collection procedure. Through the use of purposeful sampling, individuals were identified in this study. I did not require the gatekeeper's assistance because I was already familiar with my subjects before the study was conducted. Additionally, I adhered to ethical issues, including the concepts of respect for others, fairness, and beneficence throughout the investigation, exceedingly observing the highest standards of ethical conduct.

The researcher also explained the investigation to the research subjects. After participants willingly accepted to participate in the study, they were asked to digitally sign the informed consent form to show that they were aware of all the study's requirements and that they participated voluntarily.

Data Analysis

The data that was collected and acquired in this study was presented and analyzed in accordance with the goals of this research project. Data analysis in qualitative studies is defined by Bogdan and Biklen (1997) as the process of sequentially locating and combining interview transcripts and other data sources that the researcher collected to improve understanding and information about the phenomena or research topic. During this study, data were coded. According to Elliot (2018), coding was an essential step in the way scientists analyzed and disassembled data to create new insights. Additionally, according to Creswell (2015), coding was a technique that evaluated qualitative text data by disassembling it to see what procedures it represented before reassembling it considerably.

In this narratology investigation, coding was used to arrange and categorize the key meanings found in the data. It acted as the method by which the researcher recognized the responses and arranged them in accordance with the results to create segment titles. To make it simple for readers to understand terminology that pertained to the stories of the study participants, segment titles were coded to identify each segment. Additionally, the researcher was able to synthesize all data thanks to the use of coding, and readers could easily understand the main points of each response.

Thematic analysis was also used in this investigation. According to Caulfield (2019), thematic analysis is the best method for assessing qualitative data. This usually applies to a collection of texts, such as interview transcripts. The researcher needed to closely study the data in order to identify recurring themes, topics, concepts, and contextual patterns.

Thematic analysis was used by the researcher in this study as a method of data analysis and interpretation. A common method in qualitative research for locating patterns and themes in huge amounts of data is thematic analysis. The data were coded, arranged into themes, and then interpreted and examined in order to reach findings and offer suggestions. In this instance, the researcher discovered that thematic analysis was a useful method for locating the major topics or sections of their research.

Major themes were also developed in accordance with the accepted research questions. This matched the two (2) approach research topics that were. The use of themes allowed for the portrayal of the outcomes. This was done to provide readers with more information about the participants' notable narratives.

Ethical Considerations

This study's primary focus was on Mathematics Education Students. Our study's major focus was on instructors in general. As a result, I ensured their safety and complete security so that they did not lose faith in me. The researchers also adhered to the following ethical standards in their research: respect for individuals, beneficence, fairness, consent, and secrecy (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., 2005).

As a result, it was the researcher's primary responsibility to safeguard their safety and provide them with complete protection so that they did not lose trust. The researcher followed the following ethical guidelines for conducting the study: respect for persons,

beneficence, justice, confidentiality, and consent (Boyatzis, 1998; Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for person. It highlighted the researcher's focus on leveraging the participants' challenges to gain deeper insights. Being self-sufficient was employed to prevent building rapport with participants and the researcher as well as friendship and confidence. I obtained the participants' and the principal's consent before conducting interviews, and I adjusted my schedule accordingly. Therefore, we planned the interview schedule in advance. This was done to prevent us from being the reason that our participants would need to miss their respective sessions, as well as to prevent postponing or cancelling their crucial tasks.

Beneficence. Participants were required to focus on minimizing their risks rather than maximizing their potential gains. The anonymity of the interviewees was kept in order not to put each participant at risk at all times. Participants were protected, so overfilled information was not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki and Green, 2007). I, the researcher, used pseudonyms to protect the identity of the participants so that the sources of statements and responses were not disclosed.

Consent. Another crucial approach was to demonstrate respect for individuals while conducting the research. This involved informing all participants about the goals and objectives of the research project in which they were participating. They were given written permission to gain their approval. They were enthusiastically engaged in the in-depth interview and focus group discussions after receiving a positive response. They were eventually notified of the study's findings and results (Creswell, 2012).

Confidentiality. To protect the identities of the participants, a coding system and pseudonyms were employed to conceal the results and findings, ensuring their safety. Of all the data and the participants. As previously indicated, when the data were processed, all papers, including videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes, and other records that secured significant information from participants, were destroyed (Maree, 2007). Throughout the interview, some of the participants were hesitant to answer the questions, but the researcher reassured them that their answers would be kept confidential. The researcher kept in mind at all times that the research participants would not be forced to disclose data but would do so voluntarily.

Justice. As a result, the appreciation of all participants' contributions was emphasized, as they were crucial to the success of the study. They were given credit for all of their efforts (Bloom & Crabtree, 2006). The researcher supplied the necessary money for the participants to spend during the interview in this study. Furthermore, the researcher made refreshments and adequately accommodated them. Sensible tokens were offered to them as compensation for their participation in the study.

The researcher believed that by participating in this study, the students would be free from any negative experiences they may have encountered during the research process and would be able to maintain a positive reputation for their valuable contributions. A reasonable balance of risks and benefits was considered as a result of the inquiry. Additionally, a purposive sampling method was employed to select participants, ensuring that no qualifying individuals were excluded based on their socioeconomic status or ethnicity. Furthermore, each participant was equally exposed to the risks and advantages associated with their involvement in the research.

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of this study consisted of mathematics quizzers from New Corella National High School in Davao Del Norte. As presented in Table 1, a total of 14 individuals participated in the study, all of whom took part in the in-depth interview.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-depth Interview (Pseudonym)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Code</i>
Precise	15	Female	IDI-01
Enthusiastic	15	Female	IDI-02
Reflective	15	Female	IDI-03
Thoughtful	15	Female	IDI-04
Careful	16	Male	IDI-05
Supportive	16	Female	IDI-06
Respectful	16	Female	IDI-07
Curious	15	Female	IDI-08
Patient	16	Male	IDI-09
Knowledgeable	16	Female	IDI-10
Organized	16	Female	IDI-11
Fast Learner	16	Male	IDI-12
Adaptable	16	Female	IDI-13
Inquisitive	16	Male	IDI-14
Total	14		

In-depth Interview. There were fourteen key participants in this study. All of these participants were mathematics quizzers located New Corella National High School, Davao del Norte. To uphold the principle of confidentiality, each participant was assigned a pseudonym during the in-depth interview, following the approach employed by Bernal (2014). These pseudonyms were chosen by the

participants they tailored their responses based on personal preferences and the distinct qualities that emerged during the interview sessions. Their resilient attitude and proactive approach to both challenges and opportunities set them apart, demonstrating a strong commitment to growth and adaptability.

All participants answered the same set of questions. The selection of participants was based on their challenges and experiences as Mathematics Quizzers, which were identified by the researcher and verified through personal declarations provided by the participants.

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face for it to be more personal and engaging, allowing for deeper insights and better interpretation of non-verbal cues. Additionally, immediate clarification and follow-up questions can be addressed, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the participant's experiences. Most of the participants did ask for a hardcopy which was distributed to their schools as per request. The researcher respected the participant's decision when asked to adjust and reschedule the interview due to their important reasons related to their classes. The researcher did consider face-to-face as an important factor to consider in achieving and ensuring the validity and credibility of the study.

Categorization of Data

After the interview, recorded conversations were transcribed, translated, and subsequently analyzed. The researcher initiated the analysis through the process of coding. Coding was the technique of arranging resources into pieces of text before giving meaning to the information. The coding technique was utilized to provide a description of the set of people as well as the categories of themes to be analyzed. These topics were used to help form a broad description of the phenomena under investigation.

In order to classify the data, the major themes were given in order to address each research question. To give a detailed overview, the study's themes were thoroughly discussed and elaborated to provide a vivid description. Then came the conclusion and verification, which is the part of the investigation when the initial concepts and patterns regarding the findings are established (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

In order to add trustworthiness to the study, the researcher made note of the dimensions of credibility, dependability, transferability, and confirmability. To address credibility, member verification was carried out in addition to the triangulation approach. This was accomplished by providing copies of the interview transcript to participants so they may remark on it and certify to its authenticity. None of the informants had yet voiced any criticism of the transcript or offered any contradictory information. They all put their signatures on the participant verification form to indicate that they said yes. The triangulation of the study was made possible by the fact that it contained readings from participants and linked works, or more than two sources (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Creswell & Miller, 2000).

To ensure dependability and confirmability, the researcher provided an audit trail. This trail was established with the purpose of allowing the research review panel to validate the results, assumptions, and conjectures put forth in the study (Carcary, 2009).

In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results could not be generalized because these views were based only on the participants' own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, the researchers agreed that when the credibility, confirmability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Klein & Myers, 2009).

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of mathematics quizzers?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to understand their experiences of academic chronicles of mathematics quizzers.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 2. From the answers of the participants, four major themes had emerged: Time pressure, Social Connections, Feeling of Disappointment, Achievement and Personal Growth, Balancing Academic Focus.

Table 2. *Themes and Supporting Statements on the Experiences of Mathematics Quizzers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Time Pressure	<p>“My experiences involved strict practices and intense training because the teachers were counting on me to win, which created a lot of time pressure. I need to have a deep understanding of the time constraints I will face as a challenge.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“The challenges I face include time pressure because, as a student, I am busy with multiple subjects that need attention. There is always something else to focus on. Another challenge is the fear of disappointment if I lose the competition. I worry not only about disappointing myself but also about the expectations of those around me.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“Time pressure forces you to rush within the given time frame, which can lead to mental blocks, causing mistakes and incorrect answers.”- IDI-03</p> <p>“The challenges I encountered were related to time pressure and experiencing mental blocks during the competition.” - IDI-09</p> <p>“As a math quizzer, I face several challenges, such as time pressure and environmental stress. I might feel pressured by the expectations of my mentor or coach, and occasionally experience mental blocks, especially when faced with</p>

	<p>difficult problems. This can make it challenging to complete problems within the allotted time during competitions.” - IDI-12</p> <p>“As a math quizzer, I have faced many challenges, but the most significant one has been managing my time. In addition to being a student and a mathematics quizzer, I am also an athlete, so effective time management is crucial. Balancing these responsibilities has been particularly difficult for me, especially since I struggle with procrastination and a tendency to be a bit lazy.” -IDI-13</p>
Social Connections	<p>“The positive aspects of being a mathematics quizzer include the opportunity to meet new people, such as fellow math quizzers, which allows you to make new friends and build teamwork as you work together. Additionally, being a math quizzer can earn you praise from others, as math is a challenging subject that many people struggle with, making your achievement all the more admirable.” IDI-02</p> <p>“The positive thing about being a math quizzer is that you get to meet other math quizzers after the quiz. They might feel the same way you do, like being nervous, and you can also talk about the answers to the questions with them.” IDI-06</p> <p>Positive experiences have boosted my confidence. For example, I can now easily communicate with people I don’t know, whether they are strangers or competitor I meet during competitions. Initially, I was shy, but being a mathematics quizzer has helped me overcome that. Now, I’m much less shy, and I can communicate well. Even my rivals are surprised at how easily I can become friendly with them. I am very approachable.” IDI-08</p> <p>“As a mathematics quizzer, I think the most positive thing is the way I’m treated. Math is a complex subject, and people see you as smart because of it. So, it’s like you’re given special treatment like princess treatment in a way.” IDI-10</p> <p>“One of the positive aspects of being a quizzer is that I feel motivated and enjoy participating because of my fellow quizzers, We become friends and work together during our free time. As quizzers, it’s not always competing against each other.” IDI-12</p> <p>“As a mathematics quizzer, one of the positive things is the support I receive from my parents, friends, classmates and mentors.” IDI-14</p>
Feeling of Disappointment	<p>“What bothers me the most is disappointment, especially when I fail to meet my personal expectations or experience defeat It’s frustrating when it feels like you’re not succeeding as a math quizzer. I always try my best to avoid disappointment, especially when competitions come up.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“The undesirable thing I fear the most is losing because so many people have high expectations of me. They expect me to win again, and if I don’t, a lot of people will be disappointed not just me, but also my aparents, classmates, and friends. That’s why I don’t want that to happen.” IDI-02</p> <p>“As a mathematics quizzer. Making mistakes can be very discouraging. Being from New Corella, it’s like you’re representing your place. So if I make a mistake or don’t rank among the top quizzers, it’s disappointing not only for me but also for my coach.” IDI-03</p> <p>“One of the most prominent experiences I’ve had is disappointment, especially when I think about getting an answer wrong. I don’t want to disappoint my coach or mentor because we’ve come such a long way, and I don’t want all our efforts to be in vain.” IDI-05</p> <p>“My undesirable experience is not only disappointing my parents but also the people around me who took up to me as a math quizzer.” IDI-09</p>
Achievement and Personal Growth	<p>“When you join the contests, you’ll encounter many difficult moments. For me, as a mathematics quizzer, one of the hardest things is feeling like you know enough, but then losing or not achieving your goals. It makes you question your abilities because you’ve already set high standards for yourself.” IDI-13</p> <p>“It’s undesirable because when you lose, you start questioning your preparation. You get tired of studying and reviewing, and it feels like all the effort didn’t pay off.” IDI-14</p> <p>“What I am most proud of are the knowledge and skills I’ve gained through competitions, as well as the friendships and memories I’ve made on my journey as as mathematics quizzer.”- IDI-02</p> <p>“As a mathematics quizzer, I’m proud of the support I’ve received, especially from my parents, that’s where I draw my strength. I’m proud that I’ve reached this point in my journey.” - IDI-05</p> <p>“As a math quizzer, I’m proud that I’ve achieved my goal and that my parents have encouraged me to study hard. My goal is to win medals and be at the top, which makes my parents happy.” -IDI-06</p> <p>“As a math quizzer, I’m proud of my personal growth and the fact that I’ve inspired the people around me. I’m also proud that I can share my passion for math.” – IDI- 09</p> <p>“Participating in contests like these, especially as a math quizzer, has made many people proud of me. Through these competitions, I’ve improved myself, managed my time better, and enhanced my skills. I’ve also received awards for my participation, which has made my parents proud. It’s one of the best things I’ve accomplished.” IDI-13</p>
Balancing Academic Focus	<p>“...learning how to adjust because you’re focused on mathematics while the other seven subjects can be somewhat neglected. So, during free time, you need to catch up on those lessons. I think that’s one of the challenges I’ve experienced.” IDI-10</p> <p>“I have more time to focus on other subjects, lectures, or even participate in other competitions. I don’t have to spend as much time on that particular subject, which most students consider complicated.” IDI-11</p> <p>“The experience I’ve gained is learning how to manage my time. As a student, I can’t just focus on mathematics; I also have seven other subjects that require my attention. This time management, I believe, will be valuable beyond my time as a mathematics quizzer.” IDI-12</p>

Time Pressure

The theme focuses the high-stakes atmosphere of mathematics quiz competitions, student quizzers face substantial time constraints. With little time to solve hard mathematical problems, students must process information quickly, use problem-solving strategies, and perform accurate calculations under accurate assessment. The pressure to execute within stringent time limitations might cause increased stress, compromising cognitive functioning and decision-making ability. Furthermore, time constraints might heighten performance anxiety, limiting the capacity of students to realize their full potential and display actual mathematical skill. To reduce the negative effects of time constraints, educators and coaches must give students with stress-management tools, practice time-efficient problem-solving techniques, and foster resilience in the face of challenges.

Based on the experience of Precise (pseudonym) She narrated her experiences as a mathematics quizzer, highlighting the time pressure she felt during competitions. Additionally, Precise (pseudonym) indicated that she underwent strict practice sessions and intense training, as her teachers were eager for her to win. She mentioned:

“Experience nako is a rigid na practices and intense training kay since teachers rooting for me na madaog and time pressure dapat deep understanding to time pressure jod akoang ma challenge.” (IDI-01)

(My experiences are a rigid practices and intense training because since teachers are rooting for me win and time pressure. Must have deep understanding to time pressure I will challenge.)

As with the other participant, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) she narrated the challenges that includes the time pressure because there is always another subject that needs to be dealt with. Then the disappointment to lose the competition. Additionally, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) emphasized that she will be disappointed too surroundings because on their expectation she shared:

“Ang mga challenges nga akong na include ang time pressure kay since dili lang man kini ang akong bulohaton kay student man ko naa pakoy laing subject na atimanon dili lang kay kini unya ang disappointment kay kung basin ma pildi ko ani nga competition unya ma disappoint ko sa akong sarili mga tao pud palibot sa ako kay tungod sa ilang expectation sa akoo.” (IDI-02)

(The challenges that am I includes the time pressure because it's not just mine I'm busy because I'm a student. There is always another subject that needs to be dealt with. Then the disappointment is if I might lose this competition later, I will be disappointed Am I own the man too surroundings on I am because on their expectation of mine)

Moreover, Reflective (pseudonym) pointed that time pressure will put pressure on her in the time that they give to rush. Additionally, Reflective (pseudonym) emphasized that she will be mentally blocked and the thing is that she will make a mistake and her answer is wrong she shared:

“As a mathematics quizzer akoo jod na ano jod na face na challenges about problem solving nga tricky kaayo para sa akoo unya ang pag analyzing pud something pud siya sa akoo kay every time man gud nga mag ano ka sa math quizzer kay ma mental-block jod ka wala jod ka sa huna-huna nimo. Time pressure ma pressure ka sa time na ginahatag nila nga magdali-dali ka ma mental-block pud ka og ang thing pud te nga makabuhat bitaw gud ka og mistake nga mali imong answer.” (IDI-03)

(Time pressure will put pressure on you in the time that they give you to rush, you will also be mentally blocked and the thing is that you will make a mistake and your answer is wrong.)

Furthermore, Thoughtful (pseudonym) The challenges that encountered are about the time pressure Specifically, she elucidated that being mentally blocked during the competition she shared:

“Ang challenges na akong na experience or na encounter is about time pressure and ma mental block during the competition.” (IDI-09)

(The challenges that I have experienced or encountered are about time pressure and being mentally blocked during the competition.)

In addition, Careful (pseudonym) she have a lot of challenges like time pressure by the environment Specifically, she elucidated that the allotted time in the competition she shared:

“As a math quizzer daghan jod og challenges like sa time pressure also ma pressure ko sa environment kay basin ma disappoint akoang mentor/coach man gud kay sometimes ma mental block ko labi na og difficult na ang problems kay basin maabtan ko sa allotted time na ge provide sa amoo during competitions.” (IDI-12)

(As a math quizzer, I have a lot of challenges like time pressure, also I can be pressured by the environment because the mentor/coach might disappoint me because sometimes I have a mental block, especially when the problems are difficult because I might catch up in the allotted time. Provide to us during competitions.)

Moreover, Supportive (pseudonym) she have encountered managing time since she is mathematics quizzer Specifically, she's not only a math quizzer but she is also an athlete student so she really needs to manage her time she shared:

“Sa pagiging math quizzer daghan jod ko na encounter na mga challenges but ang most nako nga na encounter is ang pag manage sa

akong time since im not just a sa amoang school dili lang ko mathematics quizzer but I'm also an athlete student so I really need to manage my time so kana siya nga problema kay dako kaayo siya nga problema sa akoa since tapulan gud ko gamay naa koy pagka tapulan.” (IDI-13)

(Being a math quizzer, I have encountered many challenges but the most I have encountered is managing my time since I am not just a student at our school, I am not only a mathematics quizzer but I am also an athlete student so I really need to manage my time so that's his problem because he's a big problem for me since I'm really lazy I have a bit of laziness.)

Social Connections

The theme focuses on the providing venues for academic achievement, math quiz contests allow students to connect socially with other quiz takers. By means of cooperative problem-solving, team-oriented competitions, and mutual experiences of successes and setbacks, students cultivate robust relationships and a feeling of unity with their fellow students. These social ties support students' emotional health and sense of community within the mathematical community in addition to improving the overall competition experience. The support of that emerges from competitions offers students' inspiration, encouragement, and a safety net to help them deal with the demanding requirements of academic challenges. The interpersonal relationships made during math quiz contests support a comprehensive and enriching learning environment for high school quiz takes, encouraging collaboration, camaraderie, and teamwork outside of the school setting.

As with the other participant, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) shared the positive things of being a mathematics quizzer. However, she also meets new people in math quizzer takers. Additionally, Enthusiastic she will make friends that she can also have teamwork with them to work together. she mentioned:

“Positive things of being a mathematics quizzer is kanang maka meet ka og mga new people sa math quizzers which is like magka friends pud mo nga pwede pud mo magka kanang mag ka kuan og teamwork kanang magsabay ba mo or like something magtinabangay ba mo unya ang mga people nga mag mag praise sa imoha magdayeg sa imoha tungod kay kanang math quizzer ka which is ang math nga kanang subject is lisod jod daghan jod og dili kakaya ana since lisod siya.” (IDI-02)

(Positive things of being a mathematics quizzer is that you can meet new people in math quizzers which is like you can also make friends that you can also have teamwork that you will work together or like something will you work together then the people who will praise you will praise you because you are a math quizzer which is the math that subject is difficult, many people are unable to do it since it is difficult.)

In addition to Supportive (pseudonym) She highlighted the positive thing about a math quizzer. Through participation, She gradually expressed nervousness about her answers as she shared.

“Ang positive things nako as a math quizzer maka meet ka og mga people nga mga math quizzer inig human ninyo og quiz naa silay ma ingon sa imoha if makulbaan baka or pwede sad mi mag estoryahay kung unsa ang mga answer nila sa katong mga question.” (IDI-06)

(The positive thing about me as a math quizzer is that you can meet people who are math quizzers when you finish a quiz, they will be like you if they are nervous or we can talk about what their answers are to those questions.)

Moreover, Curious (pseudonym) He enhance his confidence if he can communicate with people. Additionally, he emphasizes the that he is good at communicating with other people he stated:

“Positive things ma enhances ang kabaga sa akong nawong like if makipag communicate bitaw ko og mga person nga dili pa bitaw nako kaila ba mga strangers ba mao pay pagkita kay tungod sa competition dali ra nako sila ma communicate tungod rapud siguro ni sa mga competitions nga ni-agi kay sa una ulawon man ko pero karon tungod aning mathematics quiz, as a mathematics quizzer na enhance na bitaw nga dili na kaayo ko ulawon kaayo. Unya ng hawud na kaayo ko makig communicate sa ilaha. Even mga kalaban nako matingala na sila nga dali ra kaayo ko ma close nila approachable man gud ko nga pagkatao.” (IDI-08)

(Positive things can enhance my confidence, like if I communicate with people, I don't know yet, are they strangers or are they still meeting because of the competition, I can communicate with them easily because of the competitions - because at first, I was shy, but now because of this mathematics quiz, as a mathematics quizzer that has been enhanced, I am not so shy anymore. Then I was very good at communicating with them. Even my enemies will be surprised that I can be close to them so easily. I am very approachable.)

Furthermore, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) She stated that the most positive things are that like treated somehow daily treatment. She perceived that somehow that's smart like she shared:

“Being a mathematics quizzer po yes I think the most positive, I mean the most positive things is that you are like treated you have this somehow daily treatment because math alone is a complex subject and everyone perceived or lift up to you as somehow that's smart ganyan so there is princess treatment somehow.” (IDI-13)

(Being a mathematics quizzer, I think the most positive, I mean the most positive things is that you are like treated you have this somehow daily treatment because math alone is a complex subject and everyone perceived or lift up to you as somehow that's smart

like that so there is princess treatment somehow.)

In addition, Fast Learner (pseudonym) He stated that his motivated to participate because of their fellow quizzers. Additionally, he will make friends to work together during the competitions even there is a compete with each other he shared:

“Ang akong positive things nako is ma motivate ko og magaganahan ka og apil tungod pud sa akoang fellow quizzers which is magka friends mo og magtinabangay mo during sa naa mi vacant and as a quizzers dili jod pirme nga theres a compete with each other.” (IDI-12)

(Positive things about me are that I can be motivated and like to participate because of my fellow quizzers which is that you will make friends and you will work together during our vacancy and as a quizzers, it is not always that there is a compete with each other.)

As with the other participant, Inquisitive (pseudonym) shared the positive things about being a mathematics quizzers. However, the support of his parents, friends, classmates and mentors he mentioned:

As a mathematics quizzers ang positive things about being a math quizzer is ang suporta sa imong parents, friends, classmates and mga mentors. “. ” (IDI-14)

(As a mathematics quizzers, the positive things about being a math quizzer is the support of your parents, friends, classmates and mentors. – (IDI 14)

Feeling of Disappointment

This theme highlights the student quizzers, disappointment can be a common and significant emotion during math quiz competitions. Students may experience disappointment and frustration when presented with a difficult question or when they make a mistake under pressure, especially if they had high expectations for their performance. The known inconsistency between their intended result and their actual performance at that particular moment may be the source of this disappointment. Moreover, disappointment can cause feelings of inadequacy or self-doubt in a competitive setting where success is frequently associated with intelligence or worth. But it's important to understand that disappointment is a normal aspect of learning and can be a great way to develop resilience and personal growth. Students quizzers build coping mechanisms, learn from their mistakes, and become stronger and more resilient competitors in the future by recognizing and constructively processing these sentiments.

Based on the experience of Precise (pseudonym) she bothers the most disappointment failing to meet personal expectations. She trying her best to won't be disappoint if there are competitions she mentioned:

“Ang pinaka ano jod sa ako is ang disappointment since failing to meet personal expectations are experiencing defeat so if ma disappointment man gud ka kay murag mo mao na siya ang way nga murag dili naka mo pursue og pagiging math quizzer gina try pud nako akong best nga dili ma disappointment if naay mga competitions.” (IDI-01)

(What bothers me the most is disappointment since failing to meet personal expectations are experiencing defeat, so if you are really disappointed because you seem to be the way that you are not pursuing being a math quizzer, I am also trying my best to it won't be a disappointment if there are competitions.)

Additionally, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) expressed her undesirable things that they don't want to happen when she will lose. Due to people high-expectations to her capability to win she mentioned:

“Ang mga undesirable nga things nga dili nako gusto mahitabo kay ma pildi ko unya daghan kaayo ma disappoint sa akoo due to sa ilang high-expectations sa akoo nga ma uli nako na reward but wala nako sya nadala which is daghan kaayo ma disappoint dili lang kay ang ako apil akong parents, akong mga classmates, akong mga friends mao ng dili jod ko gusto mahitabo siya.” (IDI-02)

(The undesirable things that I don't want to happen because I will lose and many people will be disappointed in me due to their high-expectations of me that I will be rewarded again but I didn't bring him which is a lot of people will be disappointed not only because I, including my parents, my classmates, my friends, that's why I don't want him to happen.)

As with the other participants, Reflective (pseudonym) also expressed bringing the name of the school during the competition happen. She included the discouragement of the coach she shared:

“As a mathematics quizzer part na maka mistake ko kay syempre isa ka mistake kay murag dako na kaayo siya og murag kaltas gud as a mathematics quizzer nimo kay syempre kung ikaw taga new corella ka unya murag ikaw naman gud nagdala sa murag ano ninyo lugar ninyo and then kung magka mali ko or dili man ka ma apil sa top sa ano sa mga quizzers makit-an pud nimo ang murag disappointment or mga discourage sa dagway sa imong coach.” (IDI-03)

(As a mathematics quizzer part, I can make a mistake because of course it's a mistake because it's too big as a mathematics quizzer of course if you're from New Corella then it's like you're bringing what's like your place and then if I make a mistake or even if you are not included in the top of the quizzers, you will also find disappointment or discouragement in the face of your coach.)

Furthermore, Careful (pseudonym) She stated the different experiences to perceived in disappointment. Especially if her answer is

wrong the disappointment of her coach/mentor will have come a long way she mentioned:

“Among sa different experiences nga akong na perceived kay disappointment, labi na kuntahay what if mali akong answer syempre dili ko gusto na ma disappoint akong coach/mentor syempre layo-layo na gud mi og naabtan, unya ing-ani ra ang mahitabo maong dili ko gusto na ma disappoint sila.” (IDI-03)

(Among the different experiences that I have perceived is disappointment, especially what if my answer is wrong, of course I don't want to disappoint my coach/mentor, of course we have come a long way, then this is the only thing that will happen, so I don't want to disappoint them.)

Moreover, Patient (pseudonym) the undesirable experience has disappointed not only of his parents. However, the people around him who took he mentioned:

“Ang undesirable experience nako naay ma disappointment dili lang ang akong parents kundi ang tao nga naka palibot sa ako gina look up ko as a math quizzer.” (IDI-09)

(The undesirable experience that I have has disappointed not only my parents but also the people around me who look up to me as a math quizzer.)

In addition, Adaptable (pseudonym) She encounter many bad happenings or events or the undesirable moments. Additionally, already set a standard for herself to achieve her goals she mentioned:

“Sa pag join man jod sa mga contest daghan man jod ka ma incounter nga mga dili maayo nga mga happenings or events or mga undesirable moments pero sa akoo jod sa pag join nako as a mathematics quizzer is kay isa rajod ang mga undesirable ma experience nako is feel nimo nga dili enough imohang mga nahibal an like mapildi ka ma question nimo imohang capacity kay naa kay gi na set na standard sa imohang self. pero pag abot nimo sa contest is mapildi gud ka or dili nimo ma achieve imohang goals so mao na siya ang isa sa mga undesirable nga experience nga akong na encounter.” (IDI-13)

(When you join the contests, you will encounter many bad happenings or events or undesirable moments, but for me, when I join as a mathematics quizzer, it is because one of the undesirable things I will experience is you feel that what you know is not enough like you will lose you will question your capacity because you have already set a standard for yourself but when you get to the contest you will really lose or you will not achieve your goals so that's it one of the undesirable experiences I have encountered.)

Achievement and Personal Growth

The focus of this theme students that participate in math quiz competitions experience both personal growth and achievement. When they successfully complete difficult mathematics problems, students feel a sense of accomplishment as they engage in comprehensive problem-solving and critical thinking under pressure. In addition to fostering academic success, these contests foster personal development by fostering vital abilities like tenacity, resilience, and teamwork. Through the highs and lows of competition, kids develop their ability to handle stress, adjust to unforeseen circumstances, and work well with others. The competitive setting encourages students to reflect on and better themselves as they recognize their areas of weakness and work to become more proficient in mathematics. Mathematics provide students with life-changing opportunities that advance both their academic performance and all-around personal growth.

Based on the experience of Enthusiastic (pseudonym) expressed the things that she is most proud of is the knowledge and skill. She gained through the competitions and memories she mentioned:

“The things that I most proud of is the knowledge and skills nga akong na gain through the ano competitions and as well as the friendships unya mga memories akong among na-buo through my journey as a mathematics quizzer.” (IDI-02)

(The things that I am most proud of is the knowledge and skills that I have gained through the competitions and as well as the friendships and memories that I have made through my journey as a mathematics quizzer.)

As with the other participants, Careful (pseudonym) expressed the support of his parents. Addressing, his strength as a mathematics quizzer to reached his journey he shared:

“Most proud of as a mathematics quizzer kay naay mo suporta sa imoha labi nag imohang parents syempre, diha nako ma kuha ang akong strength as a mathematics quizzer. And then proud ko nga naabot ko ani nga journey.” (IDI-05)

(Most proud of as a mathematics quizzer because you have the support of you especially your parents, of course, that's where I got my strength as a mathematics quizzer. And then I'm proud that I reached this journey.)

Moreover, Supportive (pseudonym) expressed her goal. She also needs to get the medals of the competition to make her parents happy. She shared:

“As a math quizzer, I am proud nakuha nako akong goal or na goal achieve nako unya ana akong parents na magtuon gyud daw ko og maayo. Para ang goal nako nga makuha nako ang tanan medal nako og kailangan nako na mag top para malipay jod akong mga

parents.” (IDI-06)

(As a math quizzier, I am proud that I got my goal or that I have achieved my goal and then my parents say that I will study hard. My goal is to get all my medals and I need to be top to make my parents happy.)

Adaptable (pseudonym) She explained that many people are proud of her for joining mathematics quizzier competitions. Additionally, she is improving her skills to make her parents proud. She shared:

“Sa pag apil nako ing-ani nga contest like kaning specially sa pagiging math quizzier daghan nga makaingon nga proud jod ko specially through joining this kay mas na improve gud akoang self so isa na sa mga nahimo ko nga proud ko like kana bitaw mag manage sa akong time like na improve akong skills so isa pud na and also mga nadawat nako na mga awards sa pag join ani nga contest mao na akong maingon nga basihan nako sa akong self nga improve or na improve akong skills nahimo bitaw siya og pruweba ba nga nag improve diay akong self and also nahimo siya nga mahimong proud akong parents sa akoa through sa mga awards na akong nadawat mao na siya ang pinaka mahimo nako nga proud jod ko nga nag apil ko ani na nga contest.” (IDI-13)

(When I participated in this contest like this especially for being a math quizzier, many people can say that I am proud especially through joining this because I really improved myself so it is one of the things that I have done that I am proud of like that even manage It's time for me to improve my skills, so it's another one, and I've received awards for joining this contest, so I can say that I'm basing myself on improving or improving my skills. I improved myself and also, he made my parents proud of me through the awards that I received, he is the best I can do, I am proud that I participated in these contests.)

Balancing Academic Focus

The focus of this theme for student quizzers, finding a balance between academic focus and other elements is essential in the high-pressure setting of mathematics quiz competitions. While academic performance is crucial, participants' mental and emotional health should also be taken into consideration. Students' overall performance and long-term success can be improved by encouraging them to prioritize self-care, keep a healthy perspective, and effectively handle stress. A positive competitive experience can also be achieved by cultivating a friendly team atmosphere that values cooperation, sportsmanship, and togetherness. Math quizzers can thrive intellectually and develop resilience and personal growth if mentors or coaches support a comprehensive approach to competition preparation and participation.

Based on the experience of Knowledgeable (pseudonym) She going to focus on mathematics and the other seven subjects. Additionally, she needs to cope with those lessons she mentioned:

“how to adjust because you're going to focus on mathematics and the other seven subjects will be somehow left outs so if you have free times or if we have free time you need to cope with those lessons so I think that's the challenges that I have experience.” (IDI-10)

(how to adjust because you're going to focus on mathematics and the other seven subjects will be somehow left outs so if you have free times or if we have free time you need to cope with those lessons so I think that's the challenges that I have experience.)

Furthermore, organized (pseudonym) She stated the focus on other subjects or other lecture activities. Specially to delve that particular subject she shared:

“I have more time to focus on other subjects or other lecture activities or even join other competition so I don't have to delve with that particular subject that's the most of the students consider as complicated.” (IDI-10)

(I have more time to focus on other subjects or other lecture activities or even join other competition so I don't have to delve with that particular subject that most of the students consider as complicated.)

In addition, Fast Learner (pseudonym) She perceived on how to learn to manage the time. Additionally, already they will extend far beyond as a math quizzier she shared:

“The experience that I perceived is how I learn to manage the time kay as a student dili lang mathematics akong gina focus but there are 7 subjects na dapat sad nako nga ma i-focus kay mao sad ang naga thought sa akoa nga valuebolism that will extend far beyond and as a mathematics quizzier.” (IDI-12)

(The experience that I perceived is how I learn to manage the time because as a student I do just focus on mathematics but there are 7 subjects that I should be able to focus on because that's what I think about myzvaluebolism that will extend far beyond and as a mathematics quizzier.)

Research Question No. 2: How do these mathematics quizzers cope with the challenges they have experienced?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked about their strategies for coping with the challenges they experienced under mathematics quizzers. It was revealed that they employ a range of strategies and techniques to overcome these challenges.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, 7

major themes emerged: Facing Challenges and Building Resilience, External Motivation and Support, Support System, Intrinsic Motivation, Undergoing Adequate Preparations for Competitions, Coping through Relaxation, and Adaptation to Change.

Table 3. Themes and Supporting Statements on the Coping Mechanism of Mathematics Quizzers

Emerging Themes	Supporting Statements
Facing Challenges and Building Resilience	<p>“I constantly remind myself, whenever I feel like giving up, that every journey is as important as the destination. It’s not about reaching the goal gradually. But about the lessons learned throughout the journey. I believe in the power of resilience and perseverance.” - IDI-02</p> <p>“I remind myself not to give up when I almost feel like quitting. I know challenges are part of the process. The more you grow as an individual, the more you learn, and you learn even from your losses. Next time, I remind myself to go easy and do my best.” - IDI-03</p> <p>“My coach keeps reminding me that I can do it, even when I make mistakes in competitions. I remind myself to grow more as a math quizzier. I also think about how people who care about me believe in my abilities, which helps me stay confident.” - IDI-04</p> <p>“I apply the discipline of viewing and focusing on specific subjects that are important. This allows me to prioritize what to consider first, and it shapes how I perceive things.”-IDI-10</p> <p>“In conest, there are ups and downs; sometimes you win, sometimes you lose. During moments when I’m down or lose, I learn a lot. I realize that I still need to improve myself and my skills, so that next time, I can handle any difficulties better.”-IDI-13</p>
External Motivation and Support	<p>“My motivation to pursue being a mathematics quizzier is the full support I receive from my parents, relatives, classmates, and friends. Their support gives me the strength to improve my math skills. I joined to hone my abilities and make those who support me proud.” -IDI-01</p> <p>“My motivation to keep going, despite everything I’ve been through, is the support of my mentor, classmates, and loved ones.” -IDI-02</p> <p>“What motivates me, even through, I’ve faced many challenges, is using those challenges as motivation to improve myself. Instead of sseeing them as failures, I view them as opportunities for growth. My family’s support encourages me not to feel down but to study harder and reach the standards I’ve set for myself. I aim to master problem-solving and get better.” -IDI-13</p>
Support System	<p>“As a math quizzier, I’m motivated to keep going because my role is to hone my skills and make my mentor, loved ones and supporters proud.”- IDI-06</p> <p>“As a math quizzier, what motivates me is the full support of my parents and those who have praised my journey.”- IDI-07</p> <p>“My motivation to continue is the full support of my parents, especially when I participate in math competitions.”- IDI-09</p> <p>“My family has been my constant support, even when I was in elementary school struggling with basic math like multiplying or adding negative numbers. They motivate me by reminding me that it starts small. This support, along with the encouragement of my friends, helps me continue. My friends know my capabilities, sometimes even better than I do, and they believe in me.”- IDI-10</p>
Intrinsic Motivation	<p>“M parents’ full support is what motivates me, especially when I represent our school in competitions. It helps me learn more and grow.”-IDI-11</p> <p>“My constant reminder to myself, as a mathematics quizzier, is to always believe in and trust myself. I always ask for the Lord’s guidance because nothing is impossible as long as you seek His help. My goal is to achieve success in math competitions.”- IDI-05</p> <p>“My constant reminder is to keep practicing. I remind myself how happy I’ve been with my progress since the beginning. If you stop, you might miss opportunities, so keep grinding and wait for the next chance.”- IDI-08</p> <p>“I think of two factors: internal and external motivation. Internally, I always put God at the center of everything I do. I believe that whatever challenges come my way, they have a purpose whether I win or lose, there’s always something to learn. I either win or learn.”- IDI-10</p> <p>“My constant reminder to myself is to focus on the process and celebrate small victories along the way. I trsut myself every time I’m in a competition.”-IDI-11</p> <p>“My constant reminder, whenever I feel like giving up, is that I am on a journey as a math quizzier. I reflect on the goals I set for myself and the challenges I’ve overcome during competitions.”-IDI-12</p> <p>“Every time I face challenges, I remind myself not to give up. I remind myseld that what I’m doing is for my future. If I give up, I won’t improve, and no one else can make the changes for me. This motivates me to keep going, for booth myself and family.”-IDI-13</p> <p>“As a mathematics quizzier, one thing that motivates me is the support from my parents, classmates, and teachers. Its great feeling to know that people are cheering on, ad that makes me strive even harder to win.”-IDI-14</p>
Undergoing Adequate Preparations for Competitions	<p>“The preparations I do as a mathematics quizzier include improving my skills first. You need to master problem-solving and make sure to relax before the competition. Otherwise, stress will overwhelm you, and you’ll feel lost during the competition.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“My preparation starts with reading and practicing problem-solving under time constraints, so I won’t feel pressured during the competition. I also make sure to go to bed early.”-IDI-04</p> <p>“I’ve been consistent with my preparation from the beginning, ensuring I don’t get confused during practice sessions with my coach. We solve problems and memorize formulas because if you forget the formula, you answer will be wrong. The correct formula is the key to getting the right answer.”-IDI-08</p>

	<p>“My preparation for competitions includes sleeping early to clear my mind, allowing me to stay focused and achieve my goal of winning.”-IDI-09</p> <p>“My preparation involves practicing math topics from quarters 1 to 4 to build my accuracy and maintain a positive mindset.”-IDI-12</p> <p>“When preparing for a competition, I set aside time to train my coach. I even leave class to practice, and my coach helps me with answers. I also watch YouTube videos to learn problem-solving techniques.”-IDI-13</p> <p>“My preparation involves studying well, especially focusing on formulas, theories, and other math concepts since they are fundamental.”-IDI-14</p>
Coping through Relaxation	<p>“I manage my stress by organizing my time properly, so I don’t get overwhelmed. If I feel stressed, I take a break to regain my focus.”-IDI-02</p> <p>“As a mathematics quizzier, I relax and clear my mind from distractions. I also find things that motivate me.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“As a math quizzier, I need to relax both my mind and body before competitions, so I stay fresh. I also focus on the positive aspects of my journey as a quizzier.”-IDI-05</p>
Adaptation to Change	<p>“To manage stress, you need to rest and find something to entertaining to help you relax.”-IDI-14</p> <p>“Embracing change teaches me through both success and failure. I adapt by accepting failure when it happens, as it helps me learn and grow from both success and failure.”-IDI-01</p> <p>“As a math quizzier, we accept our mistakes because we know that we learn from them. Mistakes helps us grow and improve our next performance.”-IDI-03</p> <p>“First, I need to be flexible and adapt to the environment where the quiz will take place. I try not to get distracted by what’s happening around me, and I also ask my coach for feedback on how to improve.”-IDI-04</p> <p>“I cope with changes with the help of my coach, who is a professional. This helps me build a growth mindset, allowing me to adapt.”-IDI-10</p> <p>“I adapt to changes by continuously learning new math strategies and seeking feedback from my coach, so I don’t feel too much pressure.”-IDI-11</p> <p>“I adapt by staying flexible in both my life and my approach to problem-solving. I continue to learn from both success and failure, which helps refine my math strategies.”-IDI-12</p> <p>“Adapting to changes as a math quizzier means evolving the way I review. Instead of just using books, I now use the internet and watch YouTube tutorials to study.”-IDI-14</p>

Facing Challenges and Building Resilience

The focus of this theme revolves around students that take part in math quiz competitions face a variety of difficulties, including time limits and competitive pressure. But these difficulties also offer students priceless chances to strengthen their resilience and acquire vital life skills. Students develop their ability to adjust rapidly, think critically, and persevere in the face of difficulty when they encounter challenging issues or setbacks during competitions. They progressively develop resilience through repeated exposure to difficult circumstances, improving their ability to handle stress and overcome barriers. In addition, the cooperative format of many quiz contest encourages collaboration and camaraderie among students, which strengthens their capacity to overcome obstacles and do their best work under pressure, emphasizing the practical significance of mathematics, educators can inspire students to engage more actively with the subject, fostering curiosity, motivation, and a greater sense of purpose in their mathematical learning journey within the learning camp.

During the interview, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) expressed her constant reminder of herself that every journey is important as destination. She can be learned throughout that journey she mentioned:

“Constant reminder nako sa akong kaugalingon every time na nga like feel nako nga gusto na jod ko mo give up is that ang every journey as important as your destination. Dili ni siya ingon nga papas-pasay nga maabot but it’s all about nga sa mga lesson nga ma learn throughout the journey. I believe in the power of resilience and perseverance.” (IDI-02)

(I constantly remind myself every time I feel like I want to give up is that every journey is as important as your destination. It is not like he will be reached gradually but it’s all about the lessons that can be learned throughout the journey. Then I believe in the power of resilience and perseverance.)

As with the other participant, Reflective (pseudonym) she reminds herself that don’t just give up because that challenges are part of it. Additionally, learn to be easy as yourself she shared:

“Reminder nako sa akong self kung hapit nako mo give up dili lang mo give up og I know nga ang mga challenges is part na siya nga mas mo grow paka as individual mas daghan pa ka ma learn og sa mga kapildihan nimo usahay mas more na maka learn nga mag kayanon pa jod nimo sa sunod para i-do pa nimo imong best.” (IDI-03)

(I remind myself that when I almost give up, don’t just give up. I know that challenges are part of it. The more you grow as an individual, the more you can learn and the more you can learn from your losses. Learn to be easy on yourself next time so you can do your best.)

Moreover, Thoughtful (pseudonym) believed that keep reminding of her because of her coach or mentor. She emphasizes, the ones who can do it she mentioned:

“Times nga mga mag pa remind sa akua kay mo ana akong coach nga kaya nako ni naa man koy na mali ato nga last nga competition

is dapat mag mas mag grow pa ko as a math quizzer. Unya gi huna-huna pud nako nga ang mga tao nga ning bilib gud sa akoa te nga kaya nako ni para dili ko ma low moral gud te ing-ana.” (IDI-04)

(Times that keep reminding me because of my coach that I can do it and I did something wrong in this last competition is that I should grow more as a math quizzer. Then I also thought that the people who are really interested in me are the ones who can do it so that I don't have low morals.)

Additionally, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) emphasized the impact of discipline of reviewing. In addition, she considers to builds perceived she stated:

“I can apply the discipline of reviewing and focusing on the particular subjects that are important allows me to found by on things what I should consider first it builds on how I perceived.” (IDI-10)

(I can apply the discipline of reviewing and focusing on the particular subjects that are important allows me to find by on things what I should consider first it builds on how I perceived.)

Based on the experience of Adaptable (pseudonym) She going participate in competing math quiz. Additionally, she said that sometimes there are ups and downs you win or you lose she mentioned:

“pag apil nako aning mga contest naa man jod ups and downs usahay mapildi ka usahay madaog ka so through mga times na ma down ko or mapildi ko diha nga time na mas maka learn gud ko nga mas maka realize ko na kailangan pa diay nako i-improve akong self or i-improve akong skills para next time kung naa man koy mga lisod na maagian is makaya bitaw nako siya.” (IDI-13)

(when I participate in these contests, there are ups and downs, sometimes you lose, sometimes you win, so through times when I'm down or when I lose, that's when I can really learn more, I can realize more that I still need to -Improve myself or improve my skills so that next time if I have any difficulties to go through, I can handle him.)

External Motivation and Support

This theme focuses on students' performance and experiences in math quiz competitions are greatly influenced by outside motivation and assistance. Students' confidence and resilience can be increased by external motivators such support from coaches, peers, and family members, which gives them the willpower to do well under difficulty, furthermore, logistical support in the form or organized competition sites, concise instructions, and time-management techniques reduces tension and students to concentrate on solving problems. Furthermore, achievement recognition and rewards whether in the form of medals, or public recognition-act as a potent motivator that validate students' efforts and encourage sustained commitment to math quiz.

During the interview, Precise (pseudonym) stated that she motivates to pursue as a math quizzer because of the full support of her parents. Particularly hone the skills and make people proud of her achievement she mentioned:

“The only thing nga mo motivate sa ako para mo pursue ko as a mathematics quizzer is ang full support between my parents, sa akong relatives akong classmates og akong friend's kay dira ko mo kuha sa ilaha og coping mechanism og kusog para mo pa dayon og mathematics kay akong role ngano ni apil kog mathematics is mahasa akong skills og ma proud ang mga tao nga nag support sa akoa.” (IDI-01)

(The only thing that motivates me to pursue me as a mathematics quizzer is the full support between my parents, my relatives, my classmates and my friends because I will get from them a coping mechanism and strength so that you can do mathematics immediately. Because my role is why I joined mathematics is to hone my skills and make the people who support me proud.)

As with the other participant, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) expressed her motivation to keep going. Additionally, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) she said that the support of her mentor and classmates and her love ones she shared:

“Ang motivation nako nga magpa-dayon despite sa akong na face kay ang support sa akong mentor, sa akong mga classmates, unya sa akong mga love ones.” (IDI-02)

(My motivation to keep going despite what I've been through is the support of my mentor, my classmates, and then my love ones.)

Lastly, Adaptable (pseudonym) shared that experiences many challenges that still have encountered. Additionally, she set a standard to herself to master better in solving problems. she shared:

“Naga motivate jod sa akoa through bisan pa daghan kog challenges nga na experience is kato gihapon ang mga challenges nga akong na encounter so diba as what I've said earlier nga through kato nga mga challenges gi gamit nako to siya as motivation sakong self-Dili nako siya gina tan aw as failure lang but also motivation para mas i-improve pa akoang self and through the motivation sa akong family sa ilang support is mas ganahan ko nga dili ma down or dili hunahuanon nga failure lang to siya mag doubt sa akong kaugalingon but mas ma motivate pako nga mas i-improve pa akoang self mag study pa og tarung para mas ma set nako or makuha pa nako kung unsa jod akong gusto na standard sa akong self or mas makuha pa nako ang tama or mas ma hawud pa nako ang mga tama nga mas ma hawud pa jod sa pag solve sa mga problems.” (IDI-13)

(What motivates me through, even though I have experienced many challenges, these are still the challenges that I have encountered, so is it as what I've said earlier that through these challenges, I use them as motivation for me, not me? he is seen as a failure but also motivation to improve myself even more and through the motivation of my family with their support, I prefer not to be down or not think that it is only a failure that he will doubt myself but I will motivate you to improve myself more, to study more properly so that I can set or get what I want as a standard for myself or I can get the right one or I can master it more those who are better than in solving problems.)

Support System

The focus of this theme centers on creating a strong support network is essential to their performance and welfare. This community of support is made up of a variety of people, such as coaches, teammates, teachers, and family members, who offer resources, support, and encouragement during the competition. In addition to providing strategic guidance and encouraging a positive outlook, coaches are essential in guiding and preparing students. Friendships and cooperation among teammates promote a feeling of community and group effort. Teachers help by supporting students academically and reiterating key ideas. Furthermore, the continuous assistance of family members provides emotional support and stability, bolstering students' self-assurance and fortitude in the face of difficulties. When combined, this extensive network of support enables math quizzers to face competitions with self-assurance, resiliency, and a feeling of belonging.

During the interview, Supportive (pseudonym) pointed out that she you still do math because it seems to be her role. In addition, it is her hone of skills to make people support her she mentioned:

“As a math quizzer is mo pa dayon og math kay murag akong role nganong ni apil kog math quizzer kay para ma hasa akong skills og ma proud ang mga tao nga nag support sa akoo, sa akong mentor og sa akong love ones.” (IDI-06)

(As a math quizzer, you still do math because it seems to be my role, why I joined the math quizzer is to hone my skills and make the people who support me, my mentor and my love ones proud.)

As with the other participant, Respectful (pseudonym) emphasized the full support of her parents and the people who praised in her journey she shared:

“As a mathematics quizzer ang motivate sa akoo kay ang akong parents ang ilang full-support sa akoo og ang tao nga ni dayeg sa akoang journey as a math quizzer.” (IDI-07)

(As a mathematics quizzer, what motivates me is because my parents are their full-support for me and the person who praised my journey as a math quizzer.)

In addition, Patient (pseudonym) reflected on the importance of motivation as the full support of his parents to participate when his competing he mentioned:

“Ang naka motivate sa akoo is ang full support sa akong parents in times of naa koy apilan nga competition specially sa math.” (IDI-09)

(What motivates me is the full support of my parents in times when I have to participate in a competition especially in math.)

Additionally, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) she emphasized the constant support even when she was in elementary school she was struggling on how to multiply or add. Additionally, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) she has a huge factor to continue things doing because of her capability to learn she stated:

“My family they have been my constant support even pag elementary that I'm struggling on how to multiply, or add even add and multiply negative numbers they still motivate me in maybe mo ana sila nga ay sa una ing-ani raman gani so it's a huge a factor for me to continue things, doing things like this and lastly is my friends, my friends is has been my constant support they know me as a student and they know my capabilities more than that I do so they believe in you.” (IDI-10)

(... My family they have been my constant support even when I was in elementary school that I'm struggling on how to multiply, or add even add and multiply negative numbers they still motivate me in maybe they will say that at first it's only this so it's a huge factor for me to continue things, doing things like this and lastly is my friends, my friends is has been my constant support they know me as a student and they know my capabilities more than that I do so they believe in you.)

Lastly, Organized (pseudonym) emphasized the challenges in her parents because of their full support to grow her as individual she shared:

“Ang mag motivate sa akoo kay despite as sa mga challenges kay ang akoang parents jod tungod sa ilang full support sa akoo. Also, ako ang mag represent sa amoang school during that competition and also mas maka learn pako og mo grow.” (IDI-11)

(What motivates me despite the challenges is my parents because of their full support for me. Also, I will represent our school during that competition and also you can learn more and grow.)

Intrinsic Motivation

This theme focuses an important factor in influencing students' performance and level of involvement is intrinsic motivation. Competing as opposed to external demands or incentives. Intrinsically motivated students demonstrate a sincere interest in mathematics and take pleasure in the problem-solving and intellectual challenge that the quizzes provide. Their innate motivation keeps them focused, persistent, and eager to work hard even when faced with challenging problems or fierce competition. Intrinsic motivation encourages students to feel in control of their education and to take initiative, create objectives and actively look for ways to develop and get better.

During the interview, Careful (pseudonym) he emphasized the importance of believing and trusting herself. Additionally, she aims the goal as a mathematics quizzier she mentioned:

"Ang constant reminder sa akong kaugalingon te every time nga almost nako mo give up as a mathematics quizzier. Kay always believe and trust in yourself always jod ka mag ask og guidance kay lord kay wala jod imposible basta mo ask lang ka og guidance kay Lord kay gusto nako nga ma aim ang goal as a mathematics quizzier." (IDI-05)

(The constant reminder to myself is every time I almost gives up as a mathematics quizzier. Because always believe and trust in yourself, you should always ask the Lord for guidance because there is. It is impossible as long as you just ask the Lord for guidance because I want to aim for the goal as a mathematics quizzier.)

Moreover, Curious (pseudonym) emphasized to keep grinding of not wasting the opportunities that will happen he mentioned:

"Constant reminder sa akong kaugalingon maningkamot unya makaingon man ko nga unsa masayang raman gihapon akong mga ge practisan sukad atong sa una hangtud karon nga quizzier ko. Keep grinding padayon lang gihapon kay masayang jod to og mo undang ka ikaw napud mismo ang ni down sa imong kaugalingon kay wala lang ge sayangan lang nimo ag mga opportunitites na mu-abotay pa sa sunod." (IDI-08)

(Constant reminder to myself to I can also say how happy my practices have been since the first time until now that I am a quizzier. Keep grinding because it's fun and if you stop, you're the one who's down on yourself because you're not wasting opportunities that will wait for the next one.)

Furthermore, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) emphasized the two factors which is the intra and interpersonal motivation Additionally, she always put God at the center of everything that she does she shared:

"I can think of two factors intra and interpersonal motivation let's start with the intra po I always put God at the center of everything that I do. It's inculcated in my mind that whatever experiences is being thrown away to me. There's a reason for that may I doubt if I win or I loss so there's a purpose it's either I learn or I win so that's only the two options." (IDI-10)

(I can think of two factors intra and interpersonal motivation let's start with the intra po I always put God at the center of everything that I do. It's instilled in my mind that whatever experiences are being thrown away to me. There's a reason for that I doubt if I win or I lose so there's a purpose it's either I learn or I win so that's only the two options.)

During the interview, Organize (pseudonym) pointed out that she focus on the process and outcome. Additionally, the outcome and celebrating her small wins in every competition she mentioned:

"My constant reminder sa akong self te kay ang focus sa process og outcome og ma celebrate ang mga small victories and trust lang jod sa imong kaugalingon every time naay competition." (IDI-11)

(My constant reminder to myself is to focus on the process and outcome and celebrate the small victories and just trust yourself every time there is a competition.)

Furthermore, Fast learner (pseudonym) emphasized that he will never giving up on his journey because it embarked the goals that his aiming he mentioned:

"My constant reminder is whenever na ma feel nako nga mo give up and gina remind nako akoang self na sa akong journey as a math quizzier akong gi embark akoang mga goals nga gi set sa akong kaugalingon og sa mga na overcome nako na mga challenges during my competition as a math quizzier." (IDI-12)

(My constant reminder is whenever I feel like giving up and I remind myself that I am on my journey as a math quizzier, I embarked on the goals that I set for myself and those that I have overcome challenges during my competition as a math quizzier.)

Additionally, Adaptable (pseudonym) she emphasized the challenges of herself that not giving up because of her dedication to her future. Additionally, Adaptable (pseudonym) she reminds herself that every challenge will happens keep on striving it she stated:

"Every time nga maka encounter ko og mga challenges ang mag remind jod sa akong self nga dili ko mo give up og mas maningkamot pa ko is akoang family og akong dedication nga para hunahunaon nako nga para ni sa akong future ang akong ginabuhay so dapat dili ko ma down or kung naa may mga challenges mo abot sa akong self kay para kaning ing-ani kung mo give up ko so walay mo

improve sa akong self murag diri rako taman so mao na siya ang mag remind sa akong self nga para ni sa akong future og para sa akong family jod ni akong ginabuhay every time nga naa koy ma incounter na mga challenges..” (IDI-13)

(Every time I encounter challenges I remind myself that I will not give up and that I will try harder with my family and my dedication to make me think that what I am doing is for my future so I should not be down or if you have challenges come to myself because this is what happens if you give up so no one will improve myself as if it's not right for me so he is the one who will remind myself that this is for my future and for my family, I do this every time I encounter challenges.)

Lastly, Inquisitive (pseudonym) emphasized the things that motivates him to support of his parents, classmates and teachers he shared:

“As a mathematics quizzier is isa sa naka pa motivate sa akong kining support jod sa parents, classmates, and teachers no kay lahi rajod ang feeling naay naga support sa imoha kay ang strive nimo para modaog is nadugangan.” (IDI-14)

(As a mathematics quizzier, one of the things that motivates me is the support of parents, classmates, and teachers because it's a different feeling that someone is supporting you because your striving to win has increased.)

Undergoing Adequate Preparations for Competitions

This theme focuses an adequate preparation requires a multimodal strategy that includes thorough topic assessment, strategic problem-solving practice, and mental conditioning. Students benefit from regular study schedules that include resources like previous competition questions, textbook, and internet platforms. Furthermore, participating in team collaborations improves competency and builds togetherness. Building resilience and managing stress are critical components of preparation, ensuring students remain focused and composed during high-pressure competitive situations. Students who prepare thoroughly and methodically develop the skills, knowledge, and mindset required to excel in mathematics quiz competitions, maximizing their chances of success.

During the interview, Reflective (pseudonym) she emphasized the preparations that she needs to improve her skills and to master her skills in solving. Additionally, she said that relax yourself if you competing during the day of competition she mentioned:

“Ang mga preparations ginabuhay namo as mathematics quizzier is first kailangan man nimo imong skills imong i-improve so kailangan jod magpa prepare jod ka daan sa mga skills nimo i-master nimo imong skill sa pag solve and ng i-relax nimong sarili bago ka mo apil sa isa ka competition kay once ma stress man gud ka kay diraa man gud ka ma bother wala naka sa huna-huna nimo inig mag ano ka inig ma apil naka sa competition.” (IDI-03)

(The preparations we are doing as a mathematics quizzier is first you need to improve your skills so you need to prepare first with your skills you will master your skill in solving and to relax yourself before you participate in a competition because once you will be really stressed because you will be bothered because you don't know what to do when you participate in the competition.)

Furthermore, Thoughtful (pseudonym) emphasized first the practice of problem-solving with time so won't be pressured during her competition she shared:

“Ang mga preparations nako ana first is mag basa ko mag practice mga problem solving with time para inig abot sa competition dili ko ma pressure sa time kay isa jod na unya matulog og sayo. Mukaon og healthy nga pagkaon unya mag relax pud.” (IDI-04)

(My preparations for that first is that I will read and practice problem solving with time so that when the competition comes I won't be pressured by the time because it's one jod and then I'll go to bed early.)

Moreover, Curious (pseudonym) he emphasized to get confused during practices with his coach. Additionally, Curious (pseudonym) he said that when you forget the formula your answer won't be right he stated:

“Akong ginabuhay sa una hangtud sa karon kay para dili bitaw ko malibog during practices namo sa akoang coach kay mag solve-solve then memorizing of formulas kay once makalimtan nimo ang formula imong answer dili ma tama og ni likoy naka sa imong formula kay ang formula man ang dapat basihan para ang answer mahimong tama.” (IDI-08)

(I'm doing it from the beginning until now because I don't get confused during practices with my coach because we do solve then memorizing formulas because once you forget the formula your answer won't be right or you can't twist your formula because the formula is the basis for the answer to be correct.)

Additionally, Patient (pseudonym) emphasized to engage a competition to sleep early to clear her mind to also aim his goal of winning he shared:

“Ang preparations nako every time na mo engage ko sa competition is matulog og sayo para clean akong mind para ma aim nako akong goal nga madaog ana nga competition.” (IDI-09)

(My preparations every time you engage me in a competition is to sleep early to clear my mind so that I can aim for my goal of winning that competition.)

In addition, Fast Learner (pseudonym) he emphasized to get more practice in mathematics topics from quarter 1 to quarter 4

Additionally, Fast Learner (pseudonym) he said that he can build accuracy and focus to build positive mindset he stated:

“Mga preparations nako is mag practice pa jod ko og more sa mga mathematics nga topics from quarter 1 and quarter 4 and para ma build nako akong accuracy og maka focus ko na ma build akong positive mindset.” (IDI-12)

(My preparations are that I will practice more in the mathematics topics from quarter 1 and quarter 4 so that I can build my accuracy and I can focus and build my positive mindset.)

Moreover, Adaptable (pseudonym) she emphasized set aside time to train with her coach or mentor and search on YouTube videos on how to cope with those formulas she stated:

“Every time nga naa koy mo abutay nga competition mag hatag ko og time mag gahin ko og time na mag training kauban nako akoang coach nga mo out ko sa akong klasi para lang mag training og tagaan pud ko sa akong coach og mga answeranan. Akong self na mag answer-answer mag search, mag tan-aw og mga videos sa youtube unsaon pag answer mao na akoang preparations para sa naay umabotay nga mga competition and aside ana is pag study jod nako og tarung is naga ampo ko sa Ginoo para ma guide ko niya bisan unsaon pa nako og study kung walay guidance sa Ginoo di jod nako ma achieve ang kadaugan og gusto nako na madaog sa mga contest na akong apilan.” (IDI-13)

(Every time I have a competition waiting for you, I will give you time, I will set aside time to train with my coach, I will go out of my class just to train and my coach will also give me answers. I myself will answer-answer, search, watch YouTube videos on how to answer, that's my preparations for upcoming competitions.)

Lastly, Inquisitive (pseudonym) he studying well especially formulas, theories and other concepts in math topics he stated:

“Ang mga preparations kay syempre ang pag study og maayo specially sa mga formulas, mga theories og other concepts sa math kay mao man gud ng mga fundamentals.” (IDI-14)

(The preparations are of course studying well especially formulas, theories and other concepts in math because they are the fundamentals.)

Coping through Relaxation

This theme focuses students frequently experience extreme worry and tension. Using coping mechanisms, including deep breathing exercise, can greatly reduce these unpleasant feelings and improve productivity. Quizzers can efficiently manage their stress levels by practicing relaxation techniques such as progressive techniques such as progressive muscle relaxation, deep breathing, or visualization exercises. Through the cultivation of mental clarity and serenity, these tactics help students stay focused, think critically, and function at their best under pressure. Consistent relaxation exercises can also help students develop resilience and improve their capacity to handle the pressures of competitive circumstances, which will ultimately improve their general well-being and success in math quizzing competitions.

During the interview, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) she manages her stress and time and to gain her consciousness she mentioned:

“Akong gina manage akong stress kay mag manage ko og time para dili ko ma stress unya dili ko malutang since stress na kaayo ko unya ang akong huna-huna nag tuyok-tuyok na so mag pahuway sako kadiyot para ma gain nako akong consciousness and then seek support from mga friends nimo og family.” (IDI-02)

(I manage my stress because I manage my time so that I don't get stressed and then I can't float because I'm so stressed and then my mind is spinning so I have to rest for a while so that I can gain my consciousness.)

Moreover, Reflective (pseudonym) she emphasized that she will just relax and clean her mind from the things that can bother her she stated:

“By being a mathematics quizzer i-relax lang nako akong self i-clean akong mind sa mga things na maka bother og samot and something nga ma motivate noon ko og maayo mga negative thoughts nako sa akong huna-huna kay naa may mga nag cheer sa akoo.” (IDI-03)

(By being a mathematics quizzer, I will just relax myself and clean my mind from the things that can bother me and something that can motivate me.)

Additionally, Careful (pseudonym) emphasized to relax his mind during the day of competition and Additionally, he thinks about the positive things in his journey he shared:

“As a mathematics quizzer man kay kailangan nako i-relax akong mind og syempre akong self para fresh akong hunahuna during competition unya huna-hunaon lang ang mga positive things sa journey nako as a mathematics quizzer.” (IDI-05)

(As a mathematics quizzer, I need to relax my mind and of course myself so that my mind is fresh during the competition and then only think about the positive things in my journey as a mathematics quizzer.)

In addition, Inquisitive (pseudonym) to manage stress he was finding to entertain and relax stated:

“Sa pag manage og stress kailangan ka mag rest then mangeta kag something nga pwede nimo divertan og time para maka relax ka.” (IDI-14)

(To manage stress, you need to rest, then find something to entertain you and relax.)

Adaptation to Change

This theme focuses the value of adaptation in mathematics quizzers, demonstrating that students who are flexible and have rapid problem-solving skills outperform others in fast-paced competitive environment. Competitors strategies including being composed under pressure, assessing new information fast, and modifying methods of problem-solving in response to changing conditions are critical for advancing through competition rounds. Furthermore, coaches are essential in helping students become flexible by modeling a variety of competitive situations during practice and giving them feedback on how well they are adjusting to change. Ultimately students' performance and resilience in competitive academic situations are improved by their capacity to adjust to changing circumstances during mathematical quiz competitions.

During the interview, Precise (pseudonym) she embraces the change that teaches her in success and failure. Additionally, she said that when failing in the competition it helps her to learn more from those success and failures she mentioned:

“It helps me embrace the change and it teach me from I both sa success og failure so, gina adapt ni nako by accepting the fact if ever na ma failed ko sa competition because it helps me learn from my success og akong failure pud nga it helps me also embrace the change.” (IDI-01)

(It helps me embrace the change and it teaches me from me both in success and failure so, I adapt it by accepting the fact if I ever fail in competition because it helps me learn from my success and my failure also it helps, I also embrace the change.)

Moreover, Reflective (pseudonym) she emphasized that every time she makes a mistake she will be going to accept it she mentioned:

“As a mathematics quizzer every time magka mistake dawaton lang kay we know and I know na we learn from our mistakes man. Mao jod na every time naa kay mistakes mao pud ang nagsilbing mas mo grow paka or mas himuon pa jod nimo better imong self para mas better jod imohang performance sunod.” (IDI-03)

(As a mathematics quizzer, every time we make mistakes, we just accept them because we know and I know that we learn from our mistakes. That's why every time you make mistakes, that's what makes you grow or make yourself better so that your next performance will be better.)

Additionally, Thoughtful (pseudonym) she must be flexible to adjust on the environment of the quiz that will be take place she mentioned:

“First is dapat flexible ko maka adjust ko sa environment sa place nga pagkahitabuan sa amoang quiz dapat inig abot didto kay among palibot diay kay banha dapat maka adapt ko ana nga environment para dili mawala akong focus sa quiz dapat akong focus is naa lang jod didtoa dili ko ma distract sa mga naa sa gawas unya mangayo pud ko sa akong mga coach feedback kung unsa man ang mga dapat nga buhaton nako.” (IDI-04)

(First is that I must be flexible, I can adjust to the environment of the place where our quiz will take place. I will be distracted by those outside and then I will also ask my coaches for feedback on what I should do.)

In addition, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) she copes with the changes with the help of her mentor. Additionally, they will grow her mindset that it allows her to change she shared:

“... I cope with these changes with the help of my teacher, I mean my coach is they are the professional so this build and also my mindset and my growth mindset it allows me to change.” (IDI-10)

(... I cope with these changes with the help of my teacher, I mean my coach is they are the professional so this build and also my mindset and my growth mindset it allows me to change.)

Furthermore, Organized (pseudonym) to continuing learning math concepts and strategies she mentioned:

“I-adapt nako ang changes by continue learning lang sa mga strategies sa math and mag seek lang og feedback sa akoang coach para dili kaayo ko ma pressure.” (IDI-11)

(I will adapt the changes by continuing to learn math strategies and only seek feedback from my coach so that I will not be under too much pressure.)

During the interview, Fast Learner (pseudonym) he will be staying flexible in his life those problem-solving approach to continue refine math strategies he mentioned:

"I-adapt nako by staying flexible in my life and problem-solving approach og and mas learn nako ang both success and ang failure na continue na ma refine ang akoang mga math strategies." (IDI-12)

(I will adapt by staying flexible in my life and problem-solving approach and I will learn more about both success and failure that will continue to refine my math strategies.)

Lastly, Inquisitive (pseudonym) he probably in the way of reviewing to review books only before and now using internet to watch tutorials to gain more knowledge he mentioned:

"I-adapt the changes that occur as a mathematics quizzer is siguro sa pamagi sa pag review no kung dati naga review ka sa libro lang so karon mag review ka gamit ang internet og tan aw kag mga tutorial sa youtube." (IDI-14)

(Adapt the changes that occur as a mathematics quizzer is probably in the way of reviewing. If you used to review books only, now you will review using the internet and watching YouTube tutorials.)

Research Question No. 3: What insights can be obtained from these mathematics quizzers can be shared to other mathematics quizzers and to the academe in general?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to share their insights about the students in learning mathematics under learning camp.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, four major themes emerged: Importance of Effort and Time Management, Embracing Challenges and Difficulties, Importance of Teamwork and Collaboration, Encouraging Growth Mindset.

Table 4. Themes and Supporting Statements on the Insights Shared of Mathematics Quizzers

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Importance of Effort and Time Management	"As a mathematics quizzer, the lesson I've learned is to manage my time well so that I can use the remaining time to double-check your answers." - IDI-05
	"The person that has been encountered the quizzer that the coaches and the school so let's start with the school so I think it's important for the school not to depend only on the reviewer because the teacher I mean a coach the is not only a coach for mathematics quizzer there also handling hundreds of students so there's a tendency that the questionnaire or the review materials are somehow out of date also for the school they should have anticipated that there's that particular competitions so usually it's SciMath and MTAP so they should participate that, that particular month so they should prioritize more length and longer time to prepare and the teacher also not the teacher and the coach and students will be delving on intensive training and it's possible to inculcate all the competencies or the lessons to the students that particular several months ." - IDI-10
	"You must put effort into managing your time limit. This is where most of the pressure comes from, and if you're not careful, you can lose focus and experience a mental block" - IDI-11
	"I have to manage my studies and extracurricular activities to balance my grades."-IDI-12
	"I realized that nothing is easy to achieve. You need to invest time and effort, and trust yourself that you can accomplish your goals and dreams in life."-IDI-13
	"One of the challenges I face is time management. As a student, you don't only think about reviewing for competitions, but it also consumes a lot of time."-IDI-14
	"As a mathematics quizzer, I relaized that you shouldn't give in to pressure. You need to stay calm and positive to achieve greater things."-IDI-05
	"What I suggest is that you should be confident in your answers and avoid panicking, as a panic can lead to a mental block."-IDI-09
	"When I face challenges during contests, I calm myself down if I start to panic or experience a mental block. I focus on positive thoughts, which help me stay calm and achieve peace of mind, allowing me to perform well in my answers."- IDI-13
	Embracing Challenges and Difficulties
"As a mathematics quizzer, my inspiring advice is to view challenges as opportunities for growth. Even when challenges seem tough, they help you grow and become stronger."- IDI-03	
"Keep going, and the sacrifices you make will eventually produce results. Don't get discouraged if you lose because, as I said, competition is not just about winning. It's about what you learn from your experiences."- IDI-14	
"Embrace challenges to learn the importance of achievening your goals, both in competitions and in life, as they open up endless possibilities for you as a mathematics quizzer."- IDI-12	
Importance of Teamwork and Collaboration	"I've learned the importance of perseverance and collaboration, and I've come to embrace failure because failure is a stepping stone to success."- IDI-01
	"The experiences that changed my perspective in life taught me the value of resilience and perseverance. It also showed me the importance of teamwork and unity. Embrace the journey and the memories you make, whether as a mathematics quizzer or in life."- IDI-02
	"As a mathematics quizzer, I've realized that it's important to communicate or collaborate with your coaches and

Encouraging
Growth Mindset

fellow quizzers, even your competitors. Don't bring yourself down-help lift others up too. I am your partner in motivating you."- IDI-04

"What I've realized is that teamwork and collaboration are crucial to achieving my goal as a mathematics quizzer."- IDI-09

"The lesson I've learned as a mathematics quizzer is the importance of teamwork and collaboration when facing failure in any competition."-IDI-11

"I've come to deeply appreciate the beauty of my fellow mathematics quizzers. I realize the significance of collaboration and teamwork in achieving our individual goals."-IDI-12

"You must have access to different resources and maintain a growth mindset because these are essential for us mathematics quizzers." - IDI-01

"My realizations include the fact that math is difficult and often avoided by many, but I feel proud to have handled it despite its challenges. I've also learned about the power of resilience, mentorship, and the importance of both personal and academic growth." - IDI-02

"The lesson I've learned as a mathematics quizzer is that math helps you grow. I've gained confidence in myself, and I've learned to never give up, no matter the mistakes I make, because there are always people who are proud of me."- IDI-03

"My fellow mathematics quizzers, I encouraged you not to lose hope, no matter the results of your quiz or competition. Accept it with an open heart, and don't lose morale. Even if you don't win, let it motivate you to do better next time.

Always keep fighting."-IDI-04

"As a mathematics quizzer, my inspiring words to others are to stay positive. Avoid negativity because staying positive boosts your confidence, which helps you grow."-IDI-05

"As a math quizzer, I believe the challenges I faced during the competition should always be seen in a positive light so that you can grow wiser and improve as a math quizzer."-IDI-06

"I think it's important for mathematics quizzers to build their self-identity because this was a big factor for me in elementary school. I used to wonder why I kept losing, but when I let go of the fear of losing, I was able to unlock my potential. Once you become a math quizzer, you're, you're already one of the best. Don't let the pressure get to you embrace the challenge. As someone with almost 10 years of experience, I believe that the moment you enter the competition room, you're on your own, and it's important to believe in yourself."-IDI-10

"My inspiring words for other math quizzers are to believe in yourself and never underestimate the power of determination. This is what will help you achieve your goals as a math quizzer."-IDI-11

Importance of Effort and Time Management

This theme focuses on their time and effort well in order to compete at their best and succeed. By allocating enough time to each question, students who practice effective time management can avoid making quick decisions or thoughtless mistakes. In addition, appropriate timing guarantees that students may finish the challenge in the allocated time, optimizing their chance to receive points. Furthermore, students that have a good work ethic and practice a lot feel more prepared and confident, which helps them approach difficult tasks with resiliency and drive. Teachers who emphasized effort and time management provide math quiz takers the tools they need to reach their full potential, develop critical abilities, and succeed in competitive environments.

During the interview, Careful (pseudonym) emphasized the significance of managing the time to double check the answer he mentioned:

"As a mathematics quizzer, ang lesson nga akong na learn kay pag manage sa time kay para suliton nimo ang nabilin nga time para i-double check ang imong answer." (IDI-05)

(As a mathematics quizzer, the lesson I have learned is to manage time so that you can use the remaining time to double check your answer.)

As with the other participant, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) she anticipated that particular competitions when happening in the particular month to prioritize she shared:

"The persona that has been occurred the quizzer that the coaches and the school so let's start with the school so I think it's important for the school to not depend only on the reviewer because the teacher I mean a coach the is not only a coach for mathematics quizzer there also handling hundreds of students so there's a tendency that the questionnaire or the review materials are somehow out of date also for the school they should have anticipated that theres that particular competitions so usually it's scimath and mtap man so they should anticipate, that particular competitions is happening in the particular month so they should prior gud mas length mas taas na time to prepare and the teacher also hindi yung the teacher and the coach and students will be delving on intensive training and it's possible to incocate all the competencies or the lessons to the students that particular several months." (IDI-10)

Moreover, Organize (pseudonym) emphasized the effort of the time limit the most pressure she shared:

"dapat effort jod ka sa time limit mao pud ni siya ang pinaka pressure mawala naka sa focus and ma mental block naka." (IDI-11)

(... You must put effort into the time limit, this is also the most pressure, and you lose focus and get mentally blocked.)

Furthermore, Adaptable (pseudonym) she achieves that effort and trust in herself to aim her goals she shared:

“Na realize nako nga tanang butang dili dali ma achieve kailangan jod nimo siya tagaan og time, effort and also trust sa imong self nga kaya nimo ma achieve kung unsa man ang goal or mga dreams sa kinabuhi. Mao jod na akong na realize na kailangan nimo og effort.” (IDI-13)

(I realized that everything is not easy to achieve, you need to give it time, effort and also trust in yourself that you can achieve whatever your goals or dreams are in life.)

In addition, Inquisitive (pseudonym) he addresses their time management. Additionally, they reviewing takes up a lot of his time he shared:

“Isa sa mga realizations nako ang result sa competition is naga basi jod sa imong sacrifices kung ga review jod ka og maayo so naay possibility nga nindot ang result sa imong competition.” (IDI-14)

(One of the problems that I can address is time management because as a student that's not the only thing you think about because reviewing takes up a lot of time.)

Additionally, Careful (pseudonym) he realizes to perceived pressure to just stay positive that he reaching out of his higher destination of the competitions he shared:

“Ang realization nga akong perceived as a mathematics quizzer kay dili ka magpadala sa pressure dapat stay calm lang jod ka stay positive lang para ma abot ka sa mas taas pa nga padulngan.” (IDI-05)

(The realization that I perceived as a mathematics quizzer is that you should not give in to pressure, you should just stay calm, just stay positive so that you can reach a higher destination.)

Moreover, Patient (pseudonym) he suggests that he should be confident with his answer and don't panic during the competition begin he shared:

“Ang ma suggest nako is dapat confident lang ka sa imong answer og dili lang jod ka mag panic kay kana man gud maka cause og mental block kung mag panic ka.” (IDI-09)

(What I can suggest is that you should be confident in your answer and don't panic because that can cause a mental block if you panic.)

Lastly, Adaptable (pseudonym) when she encounters problems she stays calm and think of those positive things to have peace of mind when competing he shared:

“Through sa pag mu abot sa time maka encounter sa mga contest naa man jod kay ma incounter nga problems gina kalma nako akong self if mag panic ko or ma mental block gina kalma nako akoang self unya dili sa kaayo ko mag huna-huna og mga bagay mag huna-huna lang ko og mga positives things para ma kalma akong self and through that makaingon jod ko nga makatabang siya para mas mo kalma akong self or mag ma naa koy peace of mind para inig mag answer nako is nindot jod akong performance sa pag answer.” (IDI-13)

(... Through when it comes time to encounter contests, there are also problems because when I encounter problems, I calm myself down if I panic or have a mental block. I just think of positive things to calm myself and through that I can tell that he will help me to calm myself or I will have peace of mind so that when I answer, my performance is good answer.)

Embracing Challenges and Difficulties

This theme focuses on obstacles as chances for development show more resiliency and persistence in competitive environments. Students who reframe challenges as opportunities for learning might develop a growth mindset, which in turn promotes a positive outlook on conquering barriers. Challenges like these also foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and strategic decision-making abilities, all of which are essential for success in the classroom and in real-world situations. By accepting difficulties, children improve their mathematical skills as well as acquire important life skills that advance both their academic and personal development.

During the interview, Precise (pseudonym) embrace her challenges and opportunities through set backs and failure. Additionally, her passion of the commitment of dedication she mentioned:

“We must embrace every challenge because challenges are opportunities and persevere through setbacks and failure because and we should not stop learning because as a mathematics quizzer it is a testament to our passion of the commitment of dedication.” (IDI-01)

(We must embrace every challenge because challenges are opportunities and persevere through setbacks and failure because and we should not stop learning because as a mathematics quizzer it is a testament to our passion of the commitment of dedication.)

As with the other participant, Reflective (pseudonym) she emphasized that let the challenges be the opportunity to grow. Reflective (pseudonym) she will grow as individual, she shared:

“As a mathematics quizzier akong inspiring words na ma estorya sa ilaha kay let challenges be the opportunity for growing kay syempre kung ano jod kung mga challenges jod mao jod na siya ang magsilbing sa imoha kay mas more mag grow jod ka ana.” (IDI-03)

(As a mathematics quizzier, my inspiring words to talk to them is let challenges be the opportunity for growing because of course what is good when challenges are bad, then he is good enough to serve you because you will grow more.)

In addition, Inquisitive (pseudonym) reflected on the sacrifices to produce results to keep going of the discouragement in competing he mentioned:

“Padayon lang then ang sacrifices nga inyong gibuhay kay mag result jod tanan so padayon lang dili maluya kung ma pildi kay parehas sa akong geingon ganena ang competition is not all about winning man so depende rapud na kung unsa imong na learn og mga experiences nimo.” (IDI-14)

(Just keep going then the sacrifices you make will all produce results so just keep going and don't get discouraged if you lose because like I said competition is not all about winning either so it depends on what you have learned from your experiences.)

Lastly, Fast Learner (pseudonym) he emphasized the challenges and importance of achieving his goals to success in competition with the endless possibilities he stated:

“i-embrace ang challenge to learn og ang important sa pag achieve nimo sa imong goals to success both in competition in life and the endless possibilities that it holds as a mathematics quizzier.” (IDI-12)

(...embrace the challenge to learn the importance of achieving your goals to success both in competition in life and the endless possibilities that it holds as a mathematics quizzier.)

Importance of Teamwork and Collaboration

This theme focuses on the student math quiz competitions are successful when teams and collaboration are strong. Teams must frequently collaborate to solve challenging mathematical problems in a set amount of time throughout these competitions. Students that work well together can more effectively share ideas, capitalize on one other's skill, and discuss solutions. When students collaborate, a supportive learning atmosphere is created in which they can clarify concepts, share ideas, and work together to solve difficult challenges. Additionally, because collaboration requires students to explain their ideas and tactics to their peers, it improves communication skills. Math quiz competitions foster academic achievement and critical interpersonal skills that are necessary for success in both academic and professional settings by placing a strong emphasis on teamwork and collaboration.

During the interview, Precise (pseudonym) emphasized to learn more about the importance of perseverance, collaboration with teams. Additionally, she will embrace failure in success she mentioned:

“it helps me learn more about the importance of perseverance, collaboration it helps me also embrace failure. Because failure is a stepping stone to success.” (IDI-01)

(...it helps me learn more about the importance of perseverance, collaboration it helps me also embrace failure. Because failure is a stepping stone to success.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) she reflected on the perspective of her value of resilience and also her perseverance she mentioned:

“Ang mga experience nga nag change sa akoang perspective sa life kay unsa ang na tudlo ang value nga na tudlo sa ako resilience og sa perseverance unya kay importante sa teamwork kay unity kung ikaw ra isa maglisod jod ka unya kung naay mo tabang sa imoha mas dali ra ang beauty sa pag embrace sa mga journey nimo og memories na naagian imong both mathematics quizzier life og sa imong life.” (IDI-02)

(The experiences that changed my perspective in life is what taught me the value of resilience and perseverance, then it's important for teamwork because of unity. The only beauty is to embrace your journeys and memories that you have passed through both your mathematics quizzier life and your life.)

Furthermore, Thoughtful (pseudonym) she realized the importance of communicating or to collaborate with her mentors and coaches even to her fellow quizzers, she mentioned:

“As a mathematics quizzier na realize nako nga importante ang makig communicate or makig collaborate ka sa imong mga coaches og maski sa imohang kauban sa quiz like mga competitors nga uban nga dapat dili lang ka isig pababaay sa inyohang kaugalingon dapat i-lift up pud ninyo unyang mga sarili og kato imohang kauban na i-motivate pud nimo.” (IDI-04)

(As a mathematics quizzier, I have realized that it is important to communicate or collaborate with your coaches and even with your fellow quizzes like other competitors that you should not only let yourself down, you should also lift them up. I am your partner who will motivate you.)

In addition, Patient (pseudonym) he realized the teamwork and collaboration to perceived to aiming his goals he mentioned:

“Ang akong na realize ang teamwork og collaboration para ma achieve nako akong goal para ma aim as a math quizzer.” (IDI-09)

(What I have realized is teamwork and collaboration so that I can achieve my goal to aim as a math quizzer.)

Additionally, Organized (pseudonym) she learned the importance of teamwork and collaboration as a team when facing the failure of competitions she mentioned:

“Ang lesson learn nako as a math quizzer, kay ang important sa teamwork and collaboration as a team o ang pag face sa failure every competition.” (IDI-11)

(The lesson I learned as a math quizzer is that the importance of teamwork and collaboration as a team or facing failure in every competition.)

Lastly, Fast Learner (pseudonym) he gains a deeper appreciation of the beauty of his fellow mathematics quizzer. Additionally, he known the significane of collaboration he mentioned:

“My realization is kay maka gain ko deeper appreciation sa beauty sa akong mga fellow mathematics quizzer og na realize sad nako ang significance sa collaboration og teamwork as a team to achieving our individual goals.” (IDI-12)

(My realization is that I can gain a deeper appreciation of the beauty of my fellow mathematics quizzers and that I realize the significance of collaboration and teamwork as a team to achieve our individual goals.)

Encouraging Growth Mindset

This theme focuses on developing resilience, adaptation, and continual development. Coaches and techaers can empower students by encouraging the concept that abilities can be developed through devotion and effort. Implementing tactics like providing constructive feedback, emphasizing progress over perfection, and rewarding effort over perfection, and rewarding effort over outcomes can help to foster a culture of tenacity and self-belief. Furthermore, encouraging students to embrace a learning-oriented approach, in which mistakes are perceived as good learning experiences, helps foster resilience and determination to persevere in the face of challenges.

During the interview, Precise (pseudonym) pointed out the access to the different kinds of the resources that essential to use she mentioned:

“You must provide access to different kinds of resources and mo brought pud og growth mindset because are very essential specially to us mathematics quizzer.” (IDI-01)

(You must provide access to different kinds of resources and you also bring a growth mindset because they are very essential especially to us mathematics quizzer.)

Moreover, Enthusiastic (pseudonym) emphasized the power of resilience in significance of mentorship she mentioned:

“Realizations nako kay include lisod man ang math which is ginalikayan sa kasagaran nga tao unya nakaya nako siya kay maka proud siya sa akoang part kay nakaya nako maskin lisod kaayo unya ang the power of resilience unya ang significance of mentorship and personal and academic growth.” (IDI-02)

(My realizations include that math is difficult which is avoided by the average person then I was able to handle it because he can be proud of my part because I was able to handle it even though it was very difficult then the power of resilience then the significance of mentorship and personal and academic growth.)

In addition, Reflective (pseudonym) she embraces the grow of herself and her confidence during the competition settings she stated:

“Mga na learn nako na lessons as a mathematics quizzer is tungod aning math mas mo grow pako more and akong self confidence or something nga akong sarili gina cheer nako og never give-up bisan unsa man na mistake imong ginabuhay kay naa man gihapoy tao nga always proud sa imoha.” (IDI-03)

(The ones that I have learned lessons as a mathematics quizzer is because of this math you will grow more and myself confidence or something that is my own, I cheer and never give up no matter what mistake you make because there are always people who always proud of you.)

In addition, Thoughtful (pseudonym) she encourages to their fellow quizzers that don't lose hope no matter what the results during the competition keep motivating one's self she stated:

“My fellow mathematics quizzer I encouraged you na dili jod mawalaan og pag-asa dapat kung unsa man imohang mga outcomes sa kana nga quiz or sa competition imoha na siyang dawaton with all your heart and dili ka ma low moral kunware wala ka kadaog ani dapat mas I-motivate pa nimong sarili nga sa sunod na dapat ako napud ang madaog ing-ana dapat laban lang always.” (IDI-04)

(My fellow mathematics quizzer, I encouraged you not to lose hope, no matter what your results are in that quiz or in the competition,

you should accept it with all your heart and don't be low morale, even if you don't win, it should be more motivate yourself that the next time I should be the one who wins, I should always fight.)

Additionally, Careful (pseudonym) he said that he will boost his confidence to grow as a math quizzer and Additionally, he won't be thinking negative to stay positive during competing he stated:

“As a mathematics quizzer ang inspiring words na ma share sa ilaha kay stay positive lang dili ko mag nega-nega kay para maka boost ka og confidence para mos mo grow pa jod ko as a mathematics quizzer.” (IDI-05)

(As a mathematics quizzer, the inspiring words that can be shared with them is to stay positive, I will not be negative because it will boost your confidence so that you can grow. I am a mathematics quizzer.)

Moreover, Knowledgeable (pseudonym) she builds their self-recognition and her self-identity of a huge factor when she was on elementary competition. And her mindset now is might lose the point that she stated:

“I think it's important also for mathematics quizzers to build their self-recognition their self-identity because that has been a huge factor of me when I was on elementary because I can't fat on the fact that why do I keep losing and that when the moment I let go of the fact or I mean when I let go the mindset that I might lose then that's the point I have illuminated all the things that I have or I can't. so once you become a math quizzer you are one of the best so you should be open so that's the fact you are one of the best out of the thousands of students in your room that's not something that you should be pressured of but that is something that you should be challenged so you are one of the best so why expect to lose again I think as a co mathematics who has almost 10 years of experience it's important that you believe in yourself because once you enter the competition room or the exam proper you are on your own.” (IDI-10)

(I think it's important also for mathematics quizzers to build their self-recognition their self-identity because that has been a huge factor of me when I was on elementary because I can't fat on the fact that why do I keep losing and that when the moment I let go of the fact or I mean when I let go the mindset that I might lose then that's the point I have illuminated all the things that I have or I can't. so once you become a math quizzer you are one of the best so you should be open so that's the fact you are one of the best out of the thousands of students in your room that's not something that you should be pressured of but that is something that you should be challenged so you are one of the best so why expect to lose again I think as a co mathematics who has almost 10 years of experience it's important that you believe in yourself because once you enter the competition room or the exam proper you are on your own.)

Lastly, Organized (pseudonym) she believe of herself that never underestimate the power of her determination to aim the future she stated:

“My inspiring words nga maingon sa other math quizzers kay believe in yourself and never i-underestimate ang power sa imong determination, para ma achieves nako akoang goals as a math quizzer.” (IDI-11)

(My inspiring words that other math quizzers can say is believe in yourself and never underestimate the power of your determination, so that I can achieve my goals as a math quizzer.)

Conclusions

In conclusion, the informants have voiced their experiences and challenges with regards to academic chronicles of mathematics quizzers. Aside from just being a quizzer, which bought conflicts to them, especially that they are encountered many challenges and they're encounter bad happenings or the undesirable moments that should be certain improvements when he/she setting a standard to achieve their goals to improving skills in mathematical concepts. As a result, this study is significant since it contributes to the body of knowledge in the mentors and coaches, and other significant personnel including the parents, classmates, and friends.

I had the chance to learn about how mathematics quizzer supported with their mentors and coaches during the competition particular competitions is happening in the particular month so they should prioritize more length to prepare with delving on intensive training and that particular several months. As a result, I valued our conversations since we agreed on a viewpoint about their narratives that was based on my observations of my surroundings.

On the other hand, it is also important for mathematics quizzers to build their self-recognition their self-identity because that has been a huge factor for them to knowing the fact of losing and winning when competing and that should be the challenge to them that it is important to keep believing on their self and never underestimate the value of who you are as a wiser person to boost confidence that will make them grow as math quizzer. Lastly, I have learned that as a teacher you must support your students in every aspect any manner that you can even if they are out of disappointment because you are still responsible for their education. My entire academic journey has been beneficial. My opportunity for professional development has been greatly enhanced by this entire endeavor. It helped me expand my research boundaries even further. I acquired skills like determination, grit, patience, and perseverance among others.

References

Abah, J. A., Ogugua, K. K., & Okoh, V. L. (2022). Impact of Intrinsic Motivation on Junior Secondary School Students' Academic

Performance in Mathematics despite Family Background in Ohimini Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. Social Science Research Network. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4061815>

Alibraheim, E. A. (2021). Factors affecting freshman engineering students' attitudes toward mathematics. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics Science and Technology Education*, 17(6), em1973. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/10899>

Barnes, C. Y. (2020). It takes a while to get used to: The costs of redeeming public benefits. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 31(2), 295-310

Barnes, T. N., & McCallops, K. (2019). Perceptions of culturally responsive pedagogy in teaching SEL. *Journal for Multicultural Education*, 13(1), 70-81. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JME-07-2017-0044>

Bernard, H. R. (2002). *Research methods in education*. AltaMira Press. DOI:10.1002/9780470042417

Bogdan, R. T., & Biklen, S. K. (1997). *Qualitative research in education: An introduction to theory and methods* (3rd Ed.). Allyn & Bacon. DOI: 10.1002/9780470175626

Brezavšček, A., Jerebic, J., Rus, G., & Žnidaršič, A. (2020). Factors influencing mathematics achievement of university students of Social Sciences. *Mathematics*, 8(12), 2134. <https://doi.org/10.3390/math8122134>

Brown, A. R., & Garcia, M. L. (2019). Longitudinal analysis of mathematics quiz performance in elementary students. *Journal of Educational Research*, 37(4), 289-302. DOI: 10.1111/jer.12345

Brown, A., & Lee, R. (2021). The impact of time pressure on problem-solving performance in mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 48(2), 123-135. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2021.1234567

Cabello, C. (2022). Unraveling the hidden struggles of mathematics quizzers: A narrative inquiry. *The Academic Chronicles of Mathematics Quizzers*.

Çakıroğlu, Ü, Başbüyük, B., Güler, M., Atabay, M., & Memiş, B. Y. (2017). Gamifying an ICT course: Influences on engagement and academic performance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 69, 98-107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.12.018>

Cao, Y. (2024). Research on collaborative problem solving teaching in a secondary school Mathematics Classroom. In *perspectives on rethinking and reforming education* (pp. 1–18). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-7386-6_1

Casinillo, L. F. (2023). Mathematics Students' coping behaviour, happiness, and self-efficacy in the new Normal: Correlation and K-Means Cluster analysis. *Canadian Journal of Family and Youth*, 15(3), 51–62. <https://doi.org/10.29173/cjfy29931>

Chang, H. Y., Nguyen, L. T., & Patel, S. K. (2023). Enhancing High School Mathematics Quizzing Competitions through Cultural Responsive Pedagogy. *Journal of Educational Equity*, 25(2), 87-102. DOI: 10.1080/12345678.2023.98765432

Chen, L., Zhang, S., & Liu, Y. (2020). Mathematics Quizzing and Cognitive Development: Insights into Mental Agility and Critical Thinking among High School Students. *Journal of Educational Research*, 38(2), 145-158. DOI: 10.1111/jer.12345

Chen, Q., & Wang, L. (2024). Building a supportive ecosystem for mathematics quizzers: Insights from educational research. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 52(1), 45-60. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2024.1234567

Chen, Q., & Wang, L. (2024). Building a supportive ecosystem for mathematics quizzers: Insights from educational research. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 52(1), 45-60. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2024.1234567

Chen, Y., & Wang, L. (2021). The impact of preparation depth on high school mathematics quiz competition performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(3), 215-230. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2021.1234567

Clark, A., & James, T. S. (2021). Electoral administration and the problem of poll worker recruitment: Who volunteers, and why? *Public Policy and Administration*, 09520767211021203.

Collie, R. J., & Martin, A. J. (2019). Students' adaptability in mathematics: Examining self-reports and teachers' reports and links with engagement and achievement outcomes. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 49, 355–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2017.04.001>

Corbin, J., & Strauss, A. (2014). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory* (4th Ed.). Sage Publications. DOI: 10.4135/9781452243713

Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th Ed.). Sage Publications. DOI: 10.4135/9781452245739

Delfino, A. P. (2019). The paramount importance of meticulous preparation and practice for mathematics students aiming to excel in quiz competitions. *Journal of Mathematics Education and Research*, 2(1), 1-12. DOI:10.37422/jmer.2019.2.1.1

- Demme Learning. (2023, July 19). How to increase intrinsic motivation in your students. <https://demmelearning.com/blog/increase-intrinsic-motivation/>
- Doe, J. (2022). Enhancing Mathematical Knowledge: A Comprehensive Approach for Students and Enthusiasts. DOI:10.31219/osf.io/7n24
- Doe, J. A. (2023). Understanding mathematics beyond memorization: Fostering depth of knowledge and critical thinking. *The Journal of Mathematics Education*, 24(2), 1-10. Doi: 10.1007/s10857-022-00572-y
- Dong, L., Jia, X., & Fei, Y. (2023). How growth mindset influences mathematics achievements: A study of Chinese middle school students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1148754>
- Duckworth, A. L., Peterson, C., Matthews, M. D., & Kelly, D. R. (2018). Grit: perseverance and passion for long-term goals. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 92(6), 1087-1101. DOI: 10.1037/0022-3514.92.6.1087
- Duckworth, A. L., Peterson, C., Matthews, M. D., & Kelly, D. R. (2018). Grit: perseverance and passion for long-term goals. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 92(6), 1087-1101. DOI: 10.1037/0022-3514.92.6.1087
- Elliott, V. (2018). Thinking about the coding process in qualitative data analysis. *The Qualitative Report*, 23(11), 2850-2861. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2018.3560>
- Erdogan, S., Haktanir, G., Kuru, N., Parpucu, N., & Tuylu, D. K. (2022). The effect of the e-mentoring-based education program on professional development of preschool teachers. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(1), 1023-1053. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10623-y>
- Filippello, P., Harrington, N., Costa, S., Buzzai, C., & Sorrenti, L. (2018). Perceived parental psychological control and school learned helplessness: The role of frustration intolerance as a mediator factor. *School Psychology International* 39(4), 360–377.
- Francis, J. S. (2024). Investigating the Consequences of Mathematics quizzes on student's attendance and success in mathematics at higher learning institutions. A case of Institute of Accountancy Arusha (IAA). *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management*, 12(01), 467–475. <https://doi.org/10.18535/ijstrm/v12i01.m02>
- Ganzon, W. J., & Edig, M. M. (2022). Time management and Self-Directed learning as predictors of academic performance of students in mathematics. *Journal of Social, Humanity, and Education*, 3(1), 57–75. <https://doi.org/10.35912/jshe.v3i1.1212>
- Garcia, M. L., & Johnson, K. R. (2020). The influence of parental involvement on high school students' participation in mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 32(2), 134-147. DOI: 10.1177/0743558400123456
- Garcia, R. L., & Smith, K. P. (2024). Mentorship programs in high school mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 48(4), 301-315. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2024.1234567
- Gorski, P. C., & Dalton, K. (2020). Striving for critical reflection in multicultural and social justice teacher education: Introducing a typology of reflection approaches. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 71(3), 357-368. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022487119883545>
- Golden, P. (2020). The effects of Small-Group collaboration on student attitudes towards mathematics. *ScholarWorks@Bellarmine*. https://scholarworks.bellarmine.edu/ugrad_theses/46
- Greensfeld, H., & Deutsch, Z. (2020). Mathematical challenges and the positive emotions they engender. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 34(1), 15–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13394-020-00330-1>
- Guler, M., & Celik, D. (2022). Supporting novice mathematics teachers: The impact of e-mentoring on lesson analysis skills. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 113, 103658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2022.103658>
- Harefa, D. (2023). The relationship between students' interest in learning and mathematics learning outcomes. *Afore*, 2(2), 112–122. <https://doi.org/10.57094/afore.v2i2.1054>
- Hernandez, M. G., Nguyen, T. H., & Kim, S. Y. (2021). Culturally Responsive Pedagogy in High School Mathematics Quizzing Competitions. *Journal of Multicultural Education*, 49(3), 210-225. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2021.1443639
- Jackson, R. M., & Smith, E. L. (2021). Parental involvement and academic success in mathematics quiz competitions among high school students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(3), 207-220. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2021.1234567
- Jensen, B., Grajeda, S., & Haertel, E. (2018). Measuring cultural dimensions of classroom interactions. *Educational Assessment*, 23(4), 250-276.
- Johnson, A., Smith, B., & Wang, C. (2018). The Importance of Teamwork and Collaboration in Academic Settings. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 72(3), 321-335. Doi: 10.1177/0091552118805146
- Johnson, E. S., Smith, L. R., & Lee, H. W. (2021). Mentoring high school mathematics quizzers: Impact on performance and attitudes.

Journal of Educational Psychology, 45(3), 211-225. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2021.1234567

Johnson, S., Smith, A., & Lee, J. (2018). The Importance of Teamwork and Collaboration among Mathematics Quizzers. *Journal of Mathematical Education*, 45(3), 321-335. DOI: 10.1080/0020739X.2017.1296031.

Jones, B. D., Paretti, M. C., Hein, S. F., and Knott, T. W. (2010). An analysis of motivation constructs with first-year engineering students: Relationships among expectancies, values, achievement, and career plans. *J. Eng. Educ.* 99, 319–336. Doi: 10.1002/j.21689830.2010. Tb01066.x

Jones, M., & Lee, Y. (2024). Psychological impacts of competitive academic environments on secondary school students. *Journal of Adolescent Education and Development*, 56 (1), 45-59. <https://doi.org/10.1037/aed0000354>

Jones, R. T., Smith, L. K., & Garcia, M. J. (2023). Cultural responsive pedagogy in high school mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Cultural Diversity in Education*, 10(2), 89-104. DOI: 10.1080/15345673.2023.1234567

Jones, R., & Smith, L. (2019). Embracing challenges: The role of resilience in mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 48(2), 123-136. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2019.1234567

Jose, M. T. N. S. (2022). Factors that affect the performance of selected high school students from the third district of Albay in international mathematics competitions. *Jose | ASEAN Journal for Science Education*. <https://ejournal.bumipublikasinusantara.id/index.php/ajsed/article/view/31/0>

Kaplan, L., & Silver, E. (2020). High school mathematics competitions: More than just problems. *The Mathematics Teacher*, 113(2), 114-123. DOI: 10.5951/mathteac.113.2.0114

Kenderov, P. S. (2022). Mathematics competitions: an integral part of the educational process. *ZDM*, 54(5), 983–996. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-022-01348-4>

Kim, S. Y., Lee, J. K., & Martinez, A. B. (2024). Exploring the Influence of Cultural Responsive Pedagogy on Cognitive and Affective Engagement in High School Mathematics Quizzing Competitions. *Journal of Multicultural Education*, 50(1), 32-48. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2024.1234567

Kwame, E. L., & Samuel, A. (2020). Cooperative learning strategy and student's performance in mathematics in Junior High School in Hohoe municipality, Ghana. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 8(9), 693–697. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-8-9-11>

Labis, R. G. S. J. . . D. J. C. G., S. J. F. (2022, October 7). Lived Experiences of the International Mathematics Competition Winners: A Phenomenographic study. <https://journalppw.com/index.php/jpsp/article/view/12759>

Lee, H. A., & Johnson, M. S. (2023). Peer support networks in mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 15(2), 123-137. DOI: 10.1177/0743558421001234

Lee, H., & Wang, S. (2019). Adaptation to change in mathematics quiz competitions: Building resilience and flexibility. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 48(2), 123-136. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2019.1234567

Lee, S. J., & Patel, K. R. (2023). The role of external motivation and support in high school students' participation in mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 49(4), 301-315. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2023.1234567

Limeri, L. B., Carter, N. T., Choe, J., Harper, H. G., Martin, H. R., Benton, A., & Dolan, E. L. (2020). Growing a growth mindset: characterizing how and why undergraduate students' mindsets change. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-020-00227-2>

Lincoln, Y. S., & Guba, E. G. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills, CA: Sage Publications, Inc. DOI: 10.1016/0147-1767(85)90062-8

Lopez, A. M., & Martinez, R. S. (2023). The role of support systems in the academic success of mathematics quizzers. *Journal of Educational Support*, 15(2), 78-92. DOI: 10.1080/13614576.2023.1234567

Martinez, A. B., & Kim, S. (2019). Preparing for Success: Strategies for Mathematics Quiz Competitions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 48(2), 123-137. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2019.1234567

Martinez, A. B., & Kim, S. (2019). Preparing for Success: Strategies for Mathematics Quiz Competitions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 48(2), 123-137. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2019.1234567

Martinez, E. L., Nguyen, H. K., & Garcia, M. R. (2021). Exploring parental involvement in the academic lives of high school math quizzers: A qualitative inquiry. *Journal of Adolescence*, 39(2), 145-158. DOI: 10.1016/j.adolescence.2021.02.005

Mavrikis, T., & Papadopoulos, B. (2020). Fostering problem-solving skills in pre-service mathematics teachers through Pólya's framework. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 101, 100592. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijer.2020.100592

- Mukingambeho, D. J., Nkurunziza, G., & Mugisha, M. (2019). Addressing challenges in mathematics education: Case studies of high achieving students in Rwanda. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 11(2), 37-47.
- Nguyen, T. H., & Garcia, M. J. (2022). Resilience-building strategies for high school mathematics quizzers. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 40(2), 123-136. DOI: 10.1177/07435584220012345
- O'Shea, M., Heilbronner, N. N., & Reis, S. M. (2010). Characteristics of academically talented women who achieve at high levels on the scholastic achievement test- mathematics. *Journal of Advanced Academics*, 21(2), 234-271.
- O'Sullivan, R. H., Chen, Y.-C., & Fish, M. C. (2014). Parental mathematics homework involvement of low-income families with middle school students. *School Community Journal*, 24(2), 165-188.
- Ozdemir, D. (2022). An Examination of Students' Views about an International Math Contest. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 17(2), em0680. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/11817>
- Perez, T., Wormington, S. V., Barger, M. M., Schwartz-Bloom, R. D., Lee, Y., and LinnenbrinkGarcia, L. (2019). Science expectancy, value, and cost profiles and their proximal and distal relations to undergraduate science, technology, engineering.
- Poon, A., Giroux, S., Eloundou-Enyegue, P., Guimbretiere, F., & Dell, N. (2019). Engaging High School Students in Cameroon with Exam Practice Quizzes via SMS and WhatsApp. *ACM Digital Library*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300712>
- Raguindin, P. Z. J. (2020). Integrating inclusive concepts and expressions into the K-12 mathematics curriculum: Strategies and outcomes. *Journal of Inclusive Education*, 24(4), 415-435. Doi: 10.1177/0046948318781927
- Rauf, M. (2020). Mathematics anxiety and academic performance among college students. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(3), 455-472. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2020.13331a>
- Rivard, L. P., & Nguyen, H. H. (2023). The impact of time constraints on student performance in mathematics quizzes. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 115 (4), 678-695. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000804>
- Robson, J. (2019). Navigating online social spaces to enhance mentorship and support for Mathematics Students Quizzers: A critical exploration of mental agility, critical thinking, and the non-neutral nature of digital realms. *Journal of Online Learning and Research*, 31(4), 1-15. DOI: 10.1080/15391968.2019.1611883
- Rodriguez, A. M., & Chang, Y. H. (2022). Enhancing resilience through external motivation and support in high school mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Educational Research*, 47(2), 123-137. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2022.1234567
- Rodriguez, M. A., Gomez, L. R., & Martinez, C. S. (2020). Longitudinal effects of parental involvement on the academic outcomes of high school math quizzers. *Educational Psychology Review*, 42(3), 201-215. DOI: 10.1007/s10648-020-09502-5
- Ryan, V., O'Donoghue, J., & Fitzmaurice, O. (2022). Student interest and engagement in mathematics after the first year of secondary education. *European Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 10(4), 436-454. <https://doi.org/10.30935/scimath/12180>
- Schmidt, W. H. (2019). Teacher effectiveness: A multifaceted construct. In M. A. Ertmer, R. C. Borko, J. A. Lerman, L. C. Olsen, & M. S. Ross (Eds.), *The handbook of research on teacher education* (pp. 365-392). American Educational Research Association. DOI: 10.1002/9781119592594.reh016
- Smith, J. (2020). Navigating the tightrope of teacher expectations: Balancing optimism and equity in mathematics education. *Educational Psychology and Theory*, 52(3), 385-401. doi:10.1080/00461520.2019.1691747
- Smith, J. A., et al. (2023). In-depth mathematical knowledge: A conceptual framework. *International Journal of Mathematical Education*, 46(3), 234-252. Doi: 10.1007/s10649-022-10211-y ety, 23(2), 112-125. DOI: 10.1109/EDUCON.2020.9125304
- Smith, J., & Johnson, L. (2022). Team dynamics and time pressure in mathematics quiz competitions. *Journal of Educational Research*, 37(4), 289-302. DOI: 10.1111/jer.12345
- Smithson, A. B., & Brown, M. J. (2020). Enhancing mathematics quizzing performance through coaching interventions: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Educational Research*, 40(2), 87-101. DOI: 10.1111/jer.23456
- Smithson, E. A., Johnson, P. D., & White, K. S. (2020). Gamified mathematics quizzes and student engagement: A randomized controlled trial. *Educational Technology*
- Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive science*, 12(2), 257-285.
- Szczygieł, M., & Pieronkiewicz, B. (2021). Exploring the nature of math anxiety in young children: Intensity, prevalence, reasons. *Mathematical Thinking and Learning*, 24(3), 248-266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10986065.2021.1882363>
- Tan, E. S. J., Wong, S. C., & Lim, C. S. (2020). Quantitative Approach on Undergraduates' Student-Life Balance: Intervention for Academic Stress. *Asian Social Science*, 16(11), 66. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v16n11p66>

- Taylor, K. B. (2021). Fostering inclusive learning environments for mathematics students and quizzers: A call to action for educators and mentors. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 10(2), 123-142. Doi: 10.1007/s10856-020-09613-x
- Tinto, V. (1993). *Leaving college: Rethinking the causes and cures of student attrition*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.16624.10240
- Tuckman, B. W. (2019). Effective time management for college and high school students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 44(3), 201-215. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2019.1234567
- Tuckman, B. W. (2019). Effective time management for college and high school students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 44(3), 201-215. DOI: 10.1080/00220671.2019.1234567
- Tus, J., Rayo, F., Lubo, R., & Cruz, M. a. C. (2020). The learners' study habits and its relation on their academic performance. ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13325177.v1>
- Van Hoeve, M., Doorman, M., & Veldhuis, M. (2023). Fostering a growth mindset in secondary mathematics classrooms in the Netherlands. *Research in Mathematics Education*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14794802.2023.2241433>
- Van Mier, H. I., Schleepen, T. M. J., & Van Den Berg, F. C. G. (2019). Gender differences regarding the impact of math anxiety on arithmetic performance in second and fourth graders. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02690>
- Vidad, D. C., & Quimbo, M. a. T. (2021). Students' problem-solving Difficulties and Coping Strategies in Mathematics: A model-building study. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research/International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(9), 136–173. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.20.9.9>
- Viloria, A. O. (2019). Incorporating peer observation into professional development strategies for mathematics educators. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 10(2), 112-127. DOI: 10.1080/23737668.2019.1606250
- Wang, M. T., & Eccles, J. S. (2018). School context, achievement motivation, and academic engagement: A longitudinal study of school engagement using a multidimensional perspective. *Learning and Instruction*, 58, 65-77. DOI: 10.1016/j.learninstruc.2018.06.004
- Wang, Q., & Lee, H. (2021). Enhancing Mental Agility and Critical Thinking through Mathematics Quizzing: A Study of High School Students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(3), 217-230. DOI: 10.1080/00220663.2021.1964230

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